

DEVELOPMENT, VALIDATION, AND TESTING OF VIDEO-ASSISTED INSTRUCTION IN MATHEMATICS 8

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14201852>

ABSTRACT

This study investigated the effectiveness of the developed and validated video instructional materials in developing mathematics skills and behavior (engagement, motivation, anxiety, and attitude) of grade 8 learners. It utilized a quasi-experimental research design in which the respondents are the 41 grade 8 learners in Bagupaye Integrated High School in Mulanay province of Quezon. An adopted questionnaire and researcher-made summative examinations were the tools used in gathering the data. The collected data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. Findings revealed that the developed video instructional materials have a high level of acceptability based on the evaluation of the experts. Moreover, video materials significantly improved the mathematical skills and behavior (motivation, anxiety, and attitude) of the grade 8 learners. Hence, it is recommended that teachers may strengthen the integration of videos in teaching, for these improve the mathematical skills and student behavior that may result in better academic performance.

Keywords: *Development, Validation, Testing, Learners' Behavior, Mathematical Skills*

INTRODUCTION

The development of technology has had a profound impact on numerous industries, including Education. In mathematics, technology provides interactive platforms that can make abstract concepts more understandable and engaging. Virtual manipulative and interactive software enable students to visualize complex mathematical concepts, making them more accessible and comprehensible. According to Ioannou et al. (2022), digital technologies have transformed the nature and scope of education, prompting educational systems worldwide to implement ICT integration plans and regulations. This has raised concerns about the quality of teaching and learning using ICTs, particularly regarding the comprehension, adaptation, and design of educational systems in alignment with current technological trends. The educational landscape is evolving, with a growing emphasis on leveraging technology to enhance student learning experiences and outcomes.

Mathematics plays a crucial role in developing students' logical thinking skills. To promote effective mathematical learning, teachers must consider various factors, including students' confidence in mathematics (Azucena et al., 2022; Kunhertanti & Santosa, 2018). Before the pandemic, the Philippines faced challenges in mathematics education and ranked lowest in international assessments (San Juan, 2019). Participating in the Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) for the first time in 2018, the Philippines ranked last among 79 participating countries and economies in reading and second to last in science and mathematics (World Bank, 2019). The Philippines also scored 297 in math in the 2019 Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS) by the International Association for the Evaluation of Educational Achievement (Mullis et al., 2019).

New findings from the Program for International Student Assessment (PISA) indicate that Filipino students remain among the world's weakest in math, reading, and science in the post-pandemic era. Recent test scores show no significant improvement over the country's performance in 2018. Despite the education department's extensive reforms and preparations following the poor performance in PISA 2018, less than a quarter of Filipino students who took the test in 2022 met the minimum level of proficiency in all three subjects: math, reading, and science, according to PISA results released on Tuesday (Philstar.com, 2023). Similar to 2018, the latest PISA ratings show that the Philippines performed below the global average in all categories, with its position in the country rankings rising only a few spots above countries that dropped ranks due to the pandemic's effects on student learning.

Addressing the issue of students' learning challenges in mathematics and developing effective approaches for improving mathematics education in the Philippines is crucial. In today's modern classroom, integrating technology, particularly online resources like YouTube, is critical for effective teaching and learning (Gyeltshen & Chhimi Dorji, October 2023). Hernawan, Samsuri, Kurniawati, and Sofyaningsih (2018) and Wijaya, Ying, and Suan (2020) describe video learning as a new sort of mathematics teaching resource. Video as a change agent in the classroom has followed a distinct cycle

of adoption throughout time. Video-based products encourage students' creativity and cooperation. Access to video can motivate students and provide a unique context for their learning experience (Mercado, 2022). Math films can help students improve their mathematical thinking skills by picturing math concepts, engaging in critical interpretation, and offering a forum for debate and deductive reasoning (Dejecacion, 2022). Furthermore, most students with learning challenges will make mistakes when learning mathematics. To ensure that students understand the subject, the explanation may need to be repeated. It is more difficult for teachers to explain the same thing to each student multiple times. Micro-class learning and repeated viewing can help students understand more (Wijaya, 2021). Despite these challenges, video-assisted instruction may help learners develop qualities and mathematical skills.

Several studies have been conducted on the use of video-assisted instruction as a teaching strategy in mathematics, both locally and internationally. However, no research has been conducted using teacher-made video-assisted instruction as a tool in teaching mathematics in District I Mulanay, Quezon. Furthermore, Bagupaye Integrated High School is in an area without cellular connectivity, limiting students' access to many types of social media that could be utilized for learning. Students' only means of contact are Wi-Fi and "piso Wi-Fi"; however, not all children or families in the area can connect to Wi-Fi, and not all locations have access to its line. This undertaking is necessary as schools in these districts are striving to improve the academic performance and mathematical skills of their students.

In the scenario described above, the researcher, who has served as a Grade 8 chief adviser, Mathematics Club adviser, and Grade 8 mathematics teacher for nearly four years, observed and assessed the students' abilities during the first two grading periods (1st and 2nd quarters) of S.Y. 2023–2024, employing various teaching strategies. Despite these efforts, the results showed that some students achieved numeracy scores and learning outcomes below the desired performance level of 75%. Based on the researcher's initial survey, several factors contributed to these results: some students had difficulty understanding the lessons, experienced anxiety when faced with numbers, and others felt boredom while studying and completing mathematics activities.

Given these challenges, the researcher recognizes the need to explore the use of video-assisted instruction as a potential solution to improve students' attitudes and mathematical skills. The aim is to utilize teacher-made video-assisted instruction to address the least-learned competencies, providing a solid foundation for mastering more complex mathematical concepts in the future.

The researcher believes that the findings of this study could offer valuable insights for interventions aimed at addressing the learning difficulties faced by Grade 8 students, particularly those who were in Grade 4 when the pandemic began. Teachers must support these students in becoming academically proficient in the post-pandemic context. This study ultimately aims to enhance learners' behavior and mathematical skills through video-assisted instruction.

Research Questions

This study aims to determine the development, validation, and testing of video-assisted instruction for Grade 8 Mathematics.

Specifically, it seeks to answer the following questions:

1. How are the video-assisted instruction developed in terms of:
 - 1.1 Content,
 - 1.2 Format/ Technical Design,
 - 1.3 Presentation and Organization,
 - 1.4 Accuracy and up- to- datedness of information?
2. How are the developed video-assisted instruction valid in terms of:
 - 2.1 Content,
 - 2.2 Format/ Technical Design,
 - 2.3 Presentation and Organization,
 - 2.4 Accuracy and up- to- datedness of information?
3. How is the developed video-assisted instruction tested in terms of:
 - 3.1 How is the learner's behavior described before, during, and after instruction using the developed video-assisted instruction in terms of:
 - 3.1.1 Engagement (during),
 - 3.1.2 Motivation (before and after),
 - 3.1.3 Anxiety (before and after),
 - 3.1.4 Attitude (before and after)?
 - 3.2 What is the level of Mathematical Skills of the learners before and after using the video-assisted instructions in the following MELCs:
 - 3.2.1 Illustrate relation and a function,
 - 3.2.2 Verifies if a given relation is a function,
 - 3.2.3 Determines dependent and independent variable,
 - 3.2.4 Finds the domain and range of a function,
 - 3.2.5 Determines the relationship between the hypothesis and the conclusion of an if-then statement,
 - 3.2.6 Transforms a statement into an equivalent if-then statement,
 - 3.2.7 Determine the inverse, converse, and contrapositive of an if-then statement?
4. Is there a significant difference in learners' behavior before and after using the video-assisted instruction?
5. Is there a significant difference in the mathematical skills of the learners before and after using the video-assisted instructions?
6. What are the comments and suggestions given by the validators to improve the developed video-assisted instruction?
7. Based on the findings of the study, what enhanced audio-visual material can be developed?

METHODOLOGY

This chapter presents research design, research locale, population and sample, research instrumentation, data-gathering procedures, and statistical treatment.

Research Design

This study employed a quasi-experimental research design. According to Stratton (2019), quasi-experimental design has been a standard research method for centuries. Pre-test and post-test design was a form of quasi-experimental research that allowed for uncomplicated assessment of an intervention applied to a group of study participants. A quasi-experimental design aimed to establish a cause-and-effect relationship between an independent and dependent variable. However, unlike actual experiments, a quasi-experiment did not rely on random assignment. Instead, subjects were assigned to groups based on non-random criteria (Thomas, 2020).

The research study was conducted in the second quarter of the 2024-2025 school year. The researcher aimed to develop, validate, and test video-assisted instructional materials. The study sought to assess the impact of the developed and validated video-assisted instruction on content, technical design, presentation, accuracy, and currency of information. It also analyzed the learners' behavior before, during, and after the instruction, focusing on engagement, motivation, anxiety, and attitude. Furthermore, the study evaluated the mathematical skills based on the MELCS before and after using the video-assisted instructional materials and tested for significant differences in learners' behavior pre- and post-instruction. The expected outcome was the creation of a video-assisted instruction and intervention program to enhance learners' behavior and mathematical skills. Data analysis involved frequency count, percentage mean, standard deviation, and MPS descriptive equivalent to assess the learning gains of Grade 8 students using video-assisted instruction.

Research Locale

This study was conducted in Quezon's 3rd congressional district. Quezon Province is a province in the Philippines located in the Calabarzon region of Luzon. Quezon's 3rd congressional district, also known as the Bondoc Peninsula, is one of the four congressional districts in the province of Quezon, formerly Tayabas. It has been represented in the House of Representatives of the Philippines since 1987. The district consists of municipalities in the Bondoc Peninsula, the southern part of Tayabas Isthmus, and the southwest coast of Ragay Gulf, namely Agdangan, Buenavista, Catanauan, General Luna, Macalelon, Mulanay, Padre Burgos, Pitogo, San Andres, San Francisco, San Narciso, and Unisan. It was represented in the 19th Congress by Reynante Arrogancia of the Nationalist People's Coalition.

Bagupaye Integrated High School was the site of the study. Formerly Bagupaye National High School, it is in Sitio Marasigan, Brgy. Bagupaye, Mulanay, Quezon, where the primary income of the people is farming. Mulanay, in the province of Quezon, is a first-class municipality situated 100 kilometers (62 miles) southeast of the provincial

capital, Lucena City. Administratively, the town of Mulanay is subdivided into 28 barangays, four (4) of which are urban areas. Each barangay consists of puroks, and some have sitios. As of the 2023-2024 school year, there were thirty-five teachers, three non-teaching personnel, five hundred ninety-four junior high students, and two hundred twenty-nine senior high school students.

Based on an initial survey conducted by the researchers, it was found that the main reason for these outcomes was that some students struggled to grasp the lesson, experienced anxiety when dealing with numbers, and felt disinterested during math-related activities. As a result, students did not gain a better understanding of the fundamental learning competencies, which serve as the basis for more advanced mathematical knowledge. Consequently, the researcher carried out this study at Bagupaye Integrated High School to improve education by introducing an intervention learning program in Mulanay District I, Mulanay, Quezon.

Population and Sampling

The population of the study was forty-one (41) out of 159 Grade 8 learners at Bagupaye Integrated High School, Mulanay, Quezon, who were the study's respondents and were selected through the probability sampling method. There was one independent group as the study's respondents. This group used the teacher-made video-assisted instruction based on the least learned most essential learning competencies in the second quarter.

Distribution of Respondents

Grade 8 Sections	Total Number of Students	Respondents of the study
Rose	41	41
Total	41	41

Research Instrument

The researcher used a set of questionnaires for data collection, including pre-test and post-test with video-assisted instructions, an adapted learner's behavior observation checklist for engagement, and an adapted survey questionnaire for the learner's behavior regarding motivation, anxiety, and attitude. After analyzing various studies and literature, the researcher chose to adapt Eunice Eunhee Gang's (2010) student engagement observation checklist. Additionally, an adapted questionnaire from Pintrich et al. (1991) was applied to evaluate student motivation., while a questionnaire adapted from Mutawah (2015) was used to assess student anxiety. To measure student attitude, adapted questionnaires from Aiken (1970) and Sebial (2017) were employed, consisting of two (2) parts. The researcher obtained permission to use the adopted questionnaires via email. The focus was on students' behavior and mathematical skills.

Part 1 included a set of questions that determined the learner's behavior in terms of engagement, motivation, anxiety, and attitude, for which the respondents rated the

given indicators using a 5-point Likert scale for checklist observation on engagement, a 7-point Likert scale for motivation, and a 5-point Likert scale for anxiety and attitude.

Part 2 consisted of researcher-created questions for the pre-test and post-test with video-assisted teaching. According to MELCs, the video-assisted instruction focused on the least learned learning competency among Grade 8 students. It went through construction and validation.

Construction. The researcher used researcher-made video-assisted instruction and test questions based on the least learned most essential learning competencies in the second quarter as instruments for gathering the data. The researcher employed video-assisted instruction in teaching Grade 8 students. The test questions were prepared and collected afterward. The contents of the test questions and video-assisted instruction were modified and revised accordingly after validation. The comments and suggestions were highly considered for the final editing and structuring of the video-assisted instruction and test questions, which were subsequently employed and distributed to the respondents. The researcher used test questions consisting of 30 items that aligned with the unpacking of the most essential learning competencies in the second quarter.

Validation. The researcher's video-assisted instruction and test questions were submitted to her evaluator for feedback and suggestions. The created video-assisted instruction and test questions were validated by the Master Teacher in Mathematics, Mathematics Teachers, and School Heads. After incorporating the suggestions and recommendations, the researcher delivered the final version to the validator.

Data Gathering Procedures

The researcher personally sought permission to conduct the research study from the PSDS of Mulanay District I with a letter of request. The researcher wrote a letter to obtain permission from the school head, which confirmed their agreement to allow their students to participate in the study.

Following approval, the researcher approached the teacher and school administrators to seek permission to implement video-assisted instruction. There was one section of Grade 8 students at Bagupaye Integrated High School, enrolled in the school year 2024-2025, as the respondents. Before implementing video-assisted instruction, the researcher conducted the pre-test, assessing the students' behavior in terms of motivation, anxiety, attitude, and mathematical skills. During video-assisted instruction, the observer/researcher observed the students based on the standard engagement behavior checklist. After using the video-assisted instruction, a post-test was administered to the students. The test comprised 30 item-based questions to be answered in one hour, assessing the learners' behavior and mathematical skills. It was a teacher-made test with 30 questions covering mathematics in the second quarter. The test material was tested for content validity by systematically examining its content with the Master Teacher in Mathematics. The adapted questionnaires on motivation, anxiety, and attitude were administered to the respondents after the instruction. The post-test was

conducted to determine the performance of Grade 8 students using video-assisted instruction. After administering the pre-test and post-test, the researcher collected the test materials immediately after the respondents completed the 30-item test.

For content validity, the researcher conducted a pilot implementation of the video-assisted instruction in the same schools, but not with the same grade level. An expert in mathematics carefully validated the content of the video-assisted instruction before its implementation with Grade 8 students.

The researcher developed a guide for implementing video-assisted instruction strategies before the intervention began.

Implementation of Video-Assisted Instruction

One Hour of Student Orientation. Students were required to undergo a one-hour in-person orientation on how to use video-assisted instruction. A week before the scheduled orientation, the principal and instructor sent an invitation letter to the students. The orientation included instructions on how students should behave throughout the implementation of video-assisted instruction.

Eight Weeks of Instruction. The implementation of video-assisted instruction lasted eight weeks for Grade 8 learners at Bagupaye Integrated High School. In addition, a pre-test was administered a week before the start of the video-assisted instruction.

First Week to Eighth Week. Video-assisted instruction was used daily with Grade 8 students on topics related to the Most Essential Learning Competencies (MELCs). Every Friday, the teacher administered a selected-response criterion test to assess the learners' progress on each topic throughout the eight-week instruction cycle. After eight weeks of video-assisted teaching, a post-test was given on the last Friday of the cycle.

Teacher-to-Student Feedback. Since the interventions were implemented, students received weekly feedback on their behavior and mathematical skills using video-assisted instruction. This feedback consisted of interview information and comments from the teacher, designed as systematic reinforcement for the participating students.

Statistical Treatment of Data

In Research Question 1, the development of video-assisted instruction focused on four key areas: content, format/technical design, presentation and organization, accuracy, and up-to-dateness of information. The question was answered in a narrative manner.

For Research Question 2, the validity of the video-assisted instruction was evaluated in terms of content, format/technical design, presentation and organization, accuracy, and up-to-dateness of information. The data were analyzed using mean percentage scores, standard deviation, and a scale for determining the validity level of the video-assisted instruction.

Table 1
Scale for the Validity of Video-Assisted Instruction

Scale	Mean Range	Descriptive Interpretation
4	3.26-4.00	High Level of Acceptability
3	2.51-3.25	Moderate Level of Acceptability
2	1.76-2.50	Low Level of Acceptability
1	1.00-1.75	Not Acceptable

Research Question 3 focused on describing the learners' behavior before, during, and after instruction using the developed video-assisted instruction. The data were analyzed using mean percentage scores, standard deviation, and a behavior scale for the learners.

Table 2
Scale for the Learner's Positive Behaviour Engagement

Scale	Mean Range	Description	Descriptive Interpretation
4-5	5.00 - 4.00	Always	The Student's engagement is high.
3	3.99 – 2.01	Sometimes	The Student's engagement is average.
1-2	2.00 – 1.00	Never	The Student's engagement is low.

Table 3
Scale for the Learner's Negative Engagement Behaviour Engagement

Scale	Mean Range	Description	Descriptive Interpretation
4-5	5.00 - 4.00	Always	The Student's engagement is low.
3	3.99 – 2.01	Sometimes	The Student's engagement is average.
1-2	2.00 – 1.00	Never	The Student's engagement is high.

Table 4
Scale for the Learner's Behaviour in terms of Student's Motivation

Scale	Mean Range	Descriptive Interpretation
5	4.21-5.00	The Student's motivation is very high.
4	3.41-4.20	The Student's motivation is high.
3	2.61-3.40	The Student's motivation is average.
2	1.81-2.60	The Student's motivation is low.
1	1.01-1.80	The Student's motivation is very low.

Table 5*Scale for the Learner's Behaviour in terms of Student's Anxiety*

Scale	Mean Range	Descriptive Interpretation
5	4.21-5.00	The Student's anxiety is very high.
4	3.41-4.20	The Student's anxiety is high.
3	2.61-3.40	The Student's anxiety is average.
2	1.81-2.60	The Student's anxiety is low.
1	1.01-1.80	The Student's anxiety is very low.

Table 6*Scale for the Learner's Behaviour in terms of Student's Attitude*

Scale	Mean Range	Descriptive Interpretation
5	4.21-5.00	The Student's morale is very high.
4	3.41-4.20	The Student's morale is high.
3	2.61-3.40	The Student's morale is average.
2	1.81-2.60	The Student's morale is low.
1	1.01-1.80	The Student's morale is very low.

In Research Question 4, the level of mathematical skills of the learners before and after using the video-assisted instruction (based on MELCS) in mathematics 8 second quarter of the school year 2024-2025. The data were analyzed using mean percentage scores. The indicated descriptive interpretation employed for mastery of learning competencies—the interpretative equivalent used in the National Achievement test (Deped Memorandum no. 160 s. 2012).

Table 7*The Grading Scale and its Equivalent Descriptive Interpretation*

Grading Scale	Descriptive Equivalent
96% -100%	Mastered
86% - 95%	Closely Approximating Mastery
66% - 85%	Moving Towards Mastery
35% - 65%	Average
15% - 34%	Low
5% - 14%	Very Low
0% - 5%	Absolutely No Mastery

Research Question 5 focused on the significant difference in learners' behavior before and after using the video-assisted instruction, which was tested using a paired sample t-test. This test helped determine the effectiveness of video-assisted instruction in developing learners' behavior.

In Research Question 6, the significant difference in the mathematical skills of the learners before and after using the video-assisted instruction. Which was tested using a paired sample t-test. This test helped determine the effectiveness of video-assisted instruction in developing learners' behavior.

Research Question 7 addressed the comments and suggestions provided by the validators to improve the developed video-assisted instructional materials. The question was answered narratively.

RESULTS

Part I- Development of Video-Assisted Instruction

Creating a video lesson is an excellent approach to engaging students and providing instructional knowledge in a dynamic and easily accessible format. Here are some important guidelines and formats from the Department of Education that the researcher consider in developing the video-assisted instructions in Mathematics 8.

1.1 Content

The video-assisted instruction was developed based on the most essential learning competencies in Mathematics 8. It was customized for learners, featuring specific topics that began with an introduction of objectives, a review of necessary concepts, a discussion of the topic itself, and the provision of illustrative examples and applications. Throughout the instruction, learners were also tasked with completing content-related activities. At the conclusion of each lesson, a summary of the entire topic was presented, followed by a 10-item assessment to gauge learners' comprehension.

1.2 Format/Technical Design

To make the video lesson more engaging to the learners', the researcher incorporated graphics, animations, real-life examples, and relevant images to illustrate concepts and make them more accessible to learners. The audio of the presentation is clear and crisp, contributing to a positive learning experience. Background music and sound effects further enhance the immersive and engaging atmosphere. The researcher carefully considered the pace of the video lessons, aiming for an efficient presentation of information without overwhelming learners. Recognizing that students might struggle with a rapid pace or lose interest with a slow one, the researcher sought a balance that facilitated comprehension and maintained engagement.

1.3 Presentation and Organization

The video lesson was presented bilingually, incorporating both Tagalog and English to discuss the concepts. This approach aimed to make the learning experience more effective and successful for diverse learners. The use of two languages helped to increase student engagement and reduce anxiety associated with learning mathematics. The flow of ideas was crucial in presenting the lesson, so it was carefully structured with

a deliberate order of points and smooth engaging transitions. The goal was to create a cohesive learning experience, rather than a collection of disconnected facts.

1.4 Accuracy and Up-to- datedness of Information

Recognizing the importance of accuracy, the researcher carefully reviewed all information presented in the video lessons to ensure it was correct and up-to-date. The goal was to avoid presenting any misinformation or outdated content, as errors, whether factual, grammatical, or typographical, can disrupt the learning process and lead to misunderstandings, especially since these lessons serves as a foundation for learners' higher mathematics studies.

Part II. The Validity of Video-Assisted Instruction.

2.1 Validity of Video-Assisted Instruction in Terms of Content

Table 8

Validity of Video-Assisted Instruction in Terms of Content

Statement	Mean	SD	Descriptive Interpretation
1. Content is suitable to the learner's level of development.	3.97	0.06	HLA
2. Materials contributes to the achievement of specific objectives of the learning area and grade level for which it is intended.	3.97	0.06	HLA
3. Materials provides for the development of higher cognitive skills such as critical thinking, creativity, learning by doing, inquiry, problem solving and 21 st Century Skills.	3.09	0.96	MLA
4. Materials is free of ideological, cultural, religious, racial, and gender biases and prejudices	3.43	0.55	HLA
5. Material enhances the development of desirable values and traits.	3.00	0.00	MLA
6. Materials arouses interest of target reader.	3.06	0.64	MLA
7. Adequate warning/cautionary notes are provided in topics and activities where safety and health are concern.	2.89	0.91	MLA
Weighted Mean	3.34	0.46	HLA

Legend:

3.26 – 4.00	High Level of Acceptability (HLA)
2.51-3.25	Moderate Level of Acceptability (MLA)
1.76 – 2.50	Low Level of Acceptability (LLA)
1.00 – 1.75	Not Acceptable (NA)

The table above presents the evaluation of the validity of video-assisted instructional materials in terms of content. Each statement is rated based on its mean score and standard deviation, along with the descriptive interpretation of the level of acceptability. The video-assisted instructional materials demonstrate a high level of acceptability in terms of *content suitability for the learner's developmental level and alignment with learning objectives* (M = 3.97, SD = 0.06), and the materials also exhibit a high level of acceptability in terms of *being free of biases and prejudices* (M = 3.43, SD = 0.55). However, the video-assisted instructional materials receive a moderate level of acceptability for *their contribution to the development of higher cognitive skills* (M = 3.09, SD = 0.96) this indicate that materials might provide some opportunities for higher-order thinking skills, but they may not be consistently engaging or challenging enough to encourage deep learning and critical thinking, for the *desirable values and traits* (M = 3.00, SD = 0.00) this shows that while the materials might touch upon positive values and traits, they may not be actively promoting or fostering them , and for *the materials' ability to arouse the interest of the target reader* (M = 3.43, SD = 0.55) indicating that the materials might be somewhat engaging, but they may not be consistently captivating or motivating for all viewers. The materials also show a moderate level of success in *providing adequate warning/cautionary notes for safety and health concerns* (M = 2.89, SD = 0.91) this shows that the materials might provide some warnings or cautions, but they may not be comprehensive or specific enough for all potential safety and health concerns.

A standard deviation of less than one suggests that the respondents' decisions or perceptions are consistent. This could imply that video-assisted instructional tools provide adequate opportunities for students' knowledge acquisition.

In support of this, Berry (2021) states that technology plays a crucial role in modern teaching strategies, enhancing the learning experience and improving educational outcomes. In response, incorporating video lessons as an instructional tool is crucial in today's educational landscape, as technology can effectively motivate and engage learners in the teaching-learning process.

The results in Table 8 indicate that the instructional materials are effectively tailored to the learners' needs and developmental levels, contribute significantly to achieving specific learning objectives, are relatively free of biases and prejudices, and adequately address safety and health concerns. However, the moderate degree of acceptability suggests potential for growth in areas such as activating higher cognitive skills, fostering desired values and attributes, and maintaining the target audience's interest.

Overall, the weighted mean of 3.34 reflects a positive evaluation of the content validity of the video-assisted instructional materials, highlighting strengths in various areas while also suggesting potential areas for further enhancement to ensure an even higher level of acceptability and effectiveness in supporting learning outcomes.

2.2 Validity of Video-Assisted Instruction in Terms of Format/Technical Design

Table 9

Validity of Video-Assisted Instruction in Terms of Format/Technical Design

Statement	Mean	SD	Descriptive Interpretation
1. Volume and quality of sound is appropriate	3.83	0.38	HLA
2. Pacing is effective and appropriate to instructional purposes	3.86	0.32	HLA
3. Audio-visual effects (music, sounds, graphics, etc.) are appropriate and effective for instructional purposes.	2.91	0.93	MLA
Weighted Mean	3.53	0.54	HLA

Legend:

3.26 – 4.00	High Level of Acceptability (HLA)
2.51-3.25	Moderate Level of Acceptability (MLA)
1.76 – 2.50	Low Level of Acceptability (LLA)
1.00 – 1.75	Not Acceptable (NA)

The table above shows the evaluation of the validity of video-assisted instructional materials in terms of format and technical design, yielding the following results: *The volume and sound quality* rating was 3.83, with a standard deviation of 0.38, indicating a high degree of acceptability. This suggests that reviewers found the sound elements of the video to be adequate. *The pacing of the instructional materials* received an average score of 3.86, with a standard deviation of 0.32, also indicating a high degree of acceptability. This indicates that the speed and timing of the videos were effective and appropriate for instructional use. Evaluators assessed the *audio-visual effects, which included music, sounds, and visuals*, at a mean of 2.91 with a standard deviation of 0.93. This resulted in a moderate level of acceptability, suggesting that while the effects are not ineffective, they could be improved to enhance the learning experience. This shows that there were differing perspectives on the appropriateness and efficacy of these features in improving instructional content.

The standard deviation (SD) figures indicate the variation in responses to different aspects of the video-assisted instructional materials. The SD for volume and sound quality (0.38) and pacing (0.32) were particularly low, indicating greater agreement among evaluators on these factors. However, the SD for audio-visual effects (0.93) was significantly higher, suggesting that opinions on their effectiveness and appropriateness varied widely. The overall weighted SD of 0.54 demonstrates moderate agreement across evaluators regarding all examined elements.

Overall, the weighted mean for the validity of the video-assisted instructional materials was 3.53, with a standard deviation of 0.54, indicating a high level of acceptability. This suggests that, despite some variation in scores for individual components such as audio-visual effects, the general perception of the materials' format and technical design was positive and considered appropriate for instructional purposes.

2.3 Validity of Video-Assisted Instruction in Terms of Presentation and Organization

Table 10

Validity of Video-Assisted Instruction in Terms of Presentation and Organization

Statement	Mean	SD	Descriptive Interpretation
1. Presentation is engaging, interesting, and understandable	3.49	0.55	HLA
2. There is logical and smooth flow of ideas	3.60	0.55	HLA
3. Vocabulary level is adapted to target reader's experience and understanding	3.97	0.06	HLA
4. Length of the video/audio recording is appropriate to the attention span of the target learner.	3.74	0.43	HLA
Weighted Mean	3.70	0.40	HLA

Legend:

3.26 – 4.00	High Level of Acceptability (HLA)
2.51-3.25	Moderate Level of Acceptability (MLA)
1.76 – 2.50	Low Level of Acceptability (LLA)
1.00 – 1.75	Not Acceptable (NA)

The table above shows the evaluation of the video-assisted instructional materials, which revealed a high level of acceptability across several key aspects. The presentation itself was found to be engaging, interesting, and understandable (M = 3.49, SD = 0.55) indicating a strong favourable response from the evaluators. The logical and smooth flow of ideas was also highly accepted (M = 3.60, SD = 0.55), indicating that the information was presented clearly and coherently. Furthermore, the adaptation of language level to the target audience's experience and understanding (M = 3.97, SD = 0.43) shows a strong focus on accessibility and clarity. Finally, the length of the video/audio recording was found to be extremely appropriate for the target learner's attention span (M = 3.70, SD = 0.40).

The overall mean of 3.70 indicates that the validity of the video-assisted instructional materials in terms of presentation and organization is highly acceptable, based on the results from the evaluators.

These findings suggest that the materials were thoughtfully crafted to engage and inform the intended audience, demonstrating a strong commitment to effective instructional design.

2.4 Validity of Video-Assisted Instruction in Terms Accuracy and Up-to-datedness of Information

Table 11

Validity of Video-Assisted Instruction in Terms of Accuracy and Up-to-datedness of Information

Statement	Mean	SD	Descriptive Interpretation
1. Conceptual errors	4.00	0.00	High Level of Acceptability
2. Factual errors	4.00	0.00	High Level of Acceptability
3. Grammatical errors	3.89	0.26	High Level of Acceptability
4. Computational errors	4.00	0.00	High Level of Acceptability
5. Obsolete information	3.51	0.55	High Level of Acceptability
6. Typographical and other minor errors	2.74	0.75	High Level of Acceptability
Weighted Mean	3.69	0.26	High Level of Acceptability

Legend:

3.26 – 4.00	High Level of Acceptability
2.51-3.25	Moderate Level of Acceptability
1.76 – 2.50	Low Level of Acceptability
1.00 – 1.75	Not Acceptable

Table 11 displays the evaluation of video-assisted instructional materials that are deemed to have high acceptability in terms of accuracy and timeliness of information. This result is based on the mean ($M = 4.00$, $SD = 0.00$) for conceptual, factual, and computational errors, implying that the resources are highly accurate in these areas. Despite some minor grammatical faults, the average score of 3.89, with a small standard deviation of 0.26, indicates a high degree of acceptability. Although some material may be outdated, the average score of 3.51, with a standard deviation of 0.55, for outdated information still falls within the range of high acceptability. Typographical and other minor errors received a mean score of 2.74 and a standard deviation of 0.75, indicating potential for improvement but not significantly detracting from the overall high level of acceptance of the materials.

Overall, the weighted mean of 3.69, with a standard deviation of 0.26, confirms the high level of acceptability of video-assisted instructional materials in terms of accuracy and timeliness of information.

The standard deviation (SD), being lower than 1 for each statement, indicates the consistency or variability of data points around the mean. Conceptual, factual, and computational errors demonstrate a high level of consistency and precision. Grammatical errors show slightly higher fluctuation but remain acceptable. Obsolete information exhibits slightly greater variability but is still within acceptable limits. Typographical and minor errors also have higher variability but are considered acceptable.

The findings regarding the evaluation of video-assisted instructional materials in terms of accuracy and timeliness of information are supported by Robles et al. (2019), who concluded that these video materials were substantial and could help improve students' computation skills. Therefore, the developed video-assisted instruction should be free from conceptual, factual, grammatical, computational, obsolete, and typographical errors to ensure accurate information and support learners in improving their mathematical skills.

Part III. Learner's Behaviour Described Before, During and After Instruction Using the Developed Video-Assisted Instruction.

3.1 Students' Engagement Behavior during video Presentation

Table 12

Students' Positive Engagement Behavior during video Presentation

Indicator	Video 1	Video 2	Video 3	Video 4	Video 5	Video 6	Video 7	Total		
	Mean	SD	D							
Effort										
1. Pays attention in class	4.10	3.98	3.93	3.90	4.10	2.42	2.37	3.54	.73	S
2. Works well with other children	3.42	3.68	3.85	3.76	4.10	4.15	4.24	3.89	.61	S
3. Completes assigned seatwork	3.81	4.00	3.73	3.98	3.98	4.20	4.27	3.99	.62	S
4. Is persistent when confronted with difficult problems	1.73	1.85	2.22	2.29	2.68	2.76	2.85	2.34	1.48	S
5. Approaches new assignments with sincere effort	3.32	3.34	3.76	3.73	3.83	4.15	4.20	3.76	.63	S
6. Tries to finish assignments even when they are difficult	3.73	3.73	3.83	3.90	3.98	4.20	4.24	3.94	.62	S
7. Gets discouraged and stops trying when encounter an obstacle in schoolwork; is easily frustrated	1.88	1.56	1.56	1.49	1.29	1.05	1.22	1.44	.48	N
Composite Mean	3.14	3.16	3.27	3.29	3.42	3.27	3.34	3.27	.42	S
Initiative										
1. Attempts to do his/her work thoroughly and well, rather than just trying to get by	3.44	4.00	3.90	3.98	4.12	4.24	4.29	4.00	.62	A
2. Participates actively in discussions	3.05	3.76	3.59	3.78	3.93	4.07	4.05	3.75	.81	S
3. Ask questions to get more information	3.32	3.39	3.32	3.51	3.85	4.00	4.00	3.63	.85	S

4. Raises his/her hand to answer a question or volunteer information	3.44	3.56	3.51	3.54	3.98	4.15	3.98	3.74	.85	S
Composite Mean	3.43	3.68	3.58	3.70	3.97	4.12	4.08	3.79	.70	S
GRAND MEAN	3.23	3.42	3.43	3.50	3.70	3.70	3.71	3.53	0.56	S
Description	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	S	
Legend:										
4.00 – 5.00	Always (A)	the students' engagement is high								
2.01 – 3.99	Sometimes (S)	the students' engagement is average								
1.00 – 2.00	Never (N)	the students' engagement is low								
D	Description									

The table above shows the level of student involvement during the video-assisted instructional material presentations. The data on student involvement during video-assisted teaching presentations includes several measures of students' behavior in the learning environment. For the indicator group in terms of effort, the data shows that when it comes to *paying attention in class*, the mean scores ranging from 2.37 to 4.10 across different videos suggest variability in attention levels, with a total mean of 3.54 indicating average engagement in paying attention during class sessions with a standard deviation of 0.73. Regarding *working well with other children*, scores from 3.42 to 4.24 and a total mean of 3.89 indicate average engagement in collaborating with peers, showcasing positive interactions and teamwork skills with a standard deviation of 0.61. *For completing assigned seatwork*, with scores ranging from 3.73 to 4.27 and a total mean of 3.99, students demonstrate average engagement in completing assigned tasks, highlighting their responsibility and diligence with a standard deviation of 0.62. *Persistence when faced with difficult problems* shows scores ranging from 1.73 to 2.85. A total mean of 2.34 indicates average persistence when encountering challenging issues, showing a moderate level of resilience and determination with a standard deviation of 1.48. *Approaching new assignments with sincere effort* ranges from 3.32 to 4.20, with a total mean of 3.76, showcasing average effort in tackling new tasks with a standard deviation of 0.63. *Effort in finishing difficult assignments* with scores ranging from 3.73 to 4.24 and a total mean of 3.94, students exhibit average effort in completing challenging tasks, demonstrating a willingness to overcome obstacles and a standard deviation of 0.62. Finally, *handling obstacles and frustration* ranges from 1.05 to 1.88, with a total mean of 1.44 indicating a low level of discouragement and frustration when faced with obstacles, reflecting a positive mindset and resilience in dealing with difficulties, and a standard deviation of 0.48. The overall mean scores across different video presentations for effort ranging 3.14 to 3.34, and a total mean of 3.27 with a standard deviation of 0.42, indicating that the students' level of engagement is average.

For the group of indicators in terms of initiative, the table above shows that *students strive to complete their work thoroughly and well rather than simply getting by*, with scores ranging from 3.44 to 4.29 and a total mean of 4.00 indicate high engagement in executing tasks meticulously, demonstrating a commitment to thorough work completion and a standard deviation of 0.62. *Students actively participate in the discussion*, with scores varying from 3.05 to 4.07 and a total mean of 3.75, students show average participation levels in discussions, contributing actively to academic discourse with standard deviation

of 0.81. *Asking questions for more information*, scores ranging from 3.32 to 4.00 and a total mean of 3.63 reflect a commendable effort in seeking additional information by asking insightful questions, showcasing a thirst for knowledge and understanding with a standard deviation of 0.85. Students demonstrate confidence and interest when they *raise their hands to answer inquiries or volunteer information*, with a mean scores varying from 3.44 to 4.15 and a total mean of 3.74 suggest active engagement in sharing information voluntarily, demonstrating a willingness to contribute knowledge and insights to the academic community and a standard deviation of 0.70. The overall mean across video-assisted instruction ranging from 3.43 to 4.12 indicating average to high level of students' engagement during video presentations. The total mean for initiative indicators is 3.79 suggesting an average level of students' engagement throughout the video presentations with a standard deviation of 0.70.

While the grand mean score of 3.53 and a standard deviation of 0.56 indicate a generally positive level of engagement, the overall engagement levels for both effort and initiative fall within the "Sometimes (S)" category, suggesting an average level of student engagement. Consistent composite mean scores across the videos further reinforce this observation.

By incorporating strategies that enhance behavioral engagement within video presentations, educators can leverage the positive aspects of this format while addressing the challenges identified in the data. This approach, supported by the findings of Flores et al. (2021), has the potential to improve both student engagement and academic performance in mathematics.

In conclusion, the data highlights both strengths and areas for improvement in student engagement during video presentations. By addressing challenges related to persistence and cultivating a collaborative and inquisitive learning environment, educators can further elevate student engagement levels and enhance overall learning outcomes.

Table 13
Students' Negative Engagement Behavior during video Presentation

Indicator	Video 1	Video 2	Video 3	Video 4	Video 5	Video 6	Video 7	Total		
	Mean	Mean	SD	D						
Disruptive										
1. Act restless, is unable to sit still	1.95	1.59	1.85	1.44	1.90	1.07	1.20	1.57	.68	N
2. Needs to be reprimanded	1.73	1.54	1.61	1.54	1.22	1.07	1.00	1.39	.50	N
3. Annoys or interferes with peers' work	1.63	1.46	1.49	1.34	1.24	1.05	1.00	1.32	.42	N

4. Talks with classmates too much	2.37	2.07	2.29	2.22	1.22	1.61	1.59	1.91	.62	N
Composite Mean	2.43	1.67	1.81	1.63	1.40	1.20	1.20	1.62	.55	N
Inattentive										
1. Doesn't seem to know what is going on in class	1.90	1.43	1.39	1.34	1.29	1.00	1.00	1.34	.40	N
2. Is withdrawn, uncommunicative	1.97	1.46	1.43	1.43	1.26	1.00	1.00	1.37	.40	N
3. Doesn't take independent initiative, must be helped to get started and keep going on work	1.85	1.85	1.51	1.48	1.30	1.09	1.02	1.45	.52	N
Composite Mean	1.91	1.59	1.44	1.42	1.30	1.03	1.00	1.39	.38	N
GRAND MEAN	2.17	1.63	1.63	1.53	1.35	1.16	1.1	1.51	0.56	N
Description	N	N								

Legend:

4.00 – 5.00	Always (A)	the students' engagement is low
2.01 – 3.99	Sometimes (S)	the students' engagement is average
1.00 – 2.00	Never (N)	the students' engagement is high
D	Description	

Table 13 presents the results of student's negative behavior during video presentations, categorized into disruptive and inattentive indicators. The mean scores and composite mean scores offer insights into the level of negative engagement observed across different videos.

In terms of disruptive behaviour, the results indicate that the student rarely or never *acts restless or unable to sit still* throughout the presentation, with mean scores ranging from 1.07 to 1.95. This shows that the learner is normally calm and focused. The overall mean was 1.57 and a standard deviation of 0.68. The data show that the student never *needs to be reprimanded* during the presentation, with scores ranging from 1.00 to 1.73. This means that the student is behaving appropriately and does not require frequent correction. The average mean for this statement was 1.39 and a standard deviation of 0.50. The students never *annoys or interferes with peers' work* during the presentation, with mean scores ranging from 1.00 to 1.63, indicating good behaviour and respect for others during the presentation. The overall mean score was 1.32 and the standard deviation was 0.42. The students' talks with classmates too much, with a mean score ranging from 1.22 to 2.37, were mostly rated "never," except for Videos 1, 3, and 4, where they rated it as "sometimes." The average score for this statement was 1.91 and a standard deviation of 0.62 with a verbal description of "never." The overall mean for disruptive behaviour was 1.62 and a standard deviation of 0.55.

In the group of indicators in terms of inattention, the data shows that the students "never" show that he/she *doesn't seem to know what is going on in class*, with scores

ranging from 1.00 to 1.90. This indicates that the student normally follows and comprehends the material delivered. The average mean was 1.34 and a standard deviation of 0.40. The results show that the student “Never” exhibits *withdrawn or uncommunicative behaviour*, with scores ranging from 1.00 to 1.97. This shows that the learner is actively participating and communicating during the session. The overall mean for this statement was 1.37 and a standard deviation of 0.44. The mean scores range from 1.02 to 1.85 for the statement *doesn't take independent initiative, must be helped to get started and kept going on work, indicating* that the students “never” require assistance in initiating tasks and remaining attentive during the presentation. The average inattentive behaviour is classified as never happening, with scores ranging from 1.00 to 1.91 and a total mean of 1.39 and a standard deviation of 0.38. This means that the students are attentive and concentrated during the video-assisted presentation.

The grand mean score of 1.51, with a standard deviation of 0.56, falls within the "Never (N)" category for both disruptive and inattentive indicators, indicating a high level of negative engagement among students during the video presentations. Consistent high composite mean scores across the videos further underscore this pervasive pattern of negative engagement.

By considering behavior as observable and measurable actions, as highlighted by Gilmore (2020), educators can gain valuable insights into student engagement during video presentations. This understanding can inform targeted strategies to address disruptive and inattentive behaviors, ultimately enhancing student participation and focus in educational settings.

In conclusion, student involvement during video-assisted presentations is a difficult topic that must be carefully considered in light of individual characteristics, learning styles, and the presentation's specific context. Understanding the characteristics that drive student engagement enables teachers to design more successful and interesting video-assisted learning experiences.

3.2 Students' Motivation Level Before and After Instruction Using the Developed Video-Assisted Instruction

Table 14
Students' Motivation Levels Before and After Instruction with the Developed Video-Assisted Instruction

Indicators	Mean	Before Descriptive Interpretation	Mean	After Descriptive Interpretation
1. In a class like this, I prefer course material that really challenges me so I can learn new things.	4.00	High Motivation	4.46	Very High Motivation
2. If I study in appropriate ways, then I will be able to learn the material in this course.	3.85	High Motivation	4.51	Very High Motivation
3. When I take a test, I think about how poorly I am doing compared with other students.	3.90	High Motivation	4.49	Very High Motivation

4. I think I will be able to use what I learn on this course in other courses.	4.02	High Motivation	4.80	Very High Motivation
5. I believe I will receive an excellent grade in this class.	4.15	Very High Motivation	4.17	High Motivation
6. I'm certain I can understand the most difficult material presented in the readings for this course.	3.85	High Motivation	3.98	High Motivation
7. Getting a good grade in this class is the most satisfying thing for me right now.	4.34	Very High Motivation	4.56	Very High Motivation
8. When I take a test, I think about items on other parts of the test I can't answer.	4.20	High Motivation	3.93	High Motivation
9. It is my own fault if I don't learn the material on this course.	3.59	High Motivation	4.17	High Motivation
10. It is important for me to learn the course material in this class.	4.54	Very High Motivation	4.61	Very High Motivation
11. The most important thing for me right now is improving my overall grade point average, so my main concern in this class is getting a good grade.	4.07	High Motivation	4.85	Very High Motivation
12. I'm confident I can learn the basic concepts taught on this course.	4.07	High Motivation	4.22	Very High Motivation
13. If I can, I want to get better grades in this class than most of the other students.	3.93	High Motivation	4.27	Very High Motivation
14. When I take tests, I think of the consequences of failing.	3.93	High Motivation	3.88	High Motivation
15. I'm confident I can understand the most complex material presented by the instructor in this course.	3.71	High Motivation	3.73	High Motivation
16. In a class like this, I prefer course material that arouses my curiosity, even if it is difficult to learn.	3.80	High Motivation	4.39	Very High Motivation
17. I am very interested in the content area of this course.	3.85	High Motivation	4.61	Very High Motivation
18. If I try hard enough, then I will understand the course material.	4.22	Very High Motivation	4.41	Very High Motivation
19. I have an uneasy, upset feeling when I take an exam.	3.85	High Motivation	3.80	High Motivation
20. I'm confident I can do an excellent job on the assignments and tests on this course.	4.07	High Motivation	4.49	Very High Motivation
21. I expect to do well in this class.	4.07	High Motivation	4.39	Very High Motivation
22. The most satisfying thing for me in this course is trying to understand the content as thoroughly as possible.	4.10	High Motivation	4.41	Very High Motivation
23. I think the course material in this class is useful for me to learn.	4.29	Very High Motivation	4.59	Very High Motivation
24. When I have the opportunity in this class, I choose course assignments that I can learn from even if they don't guarantee a good grade.	3.85	High Motivation	4.05	High Motivation
25. If I don't understand the course material, it is because I didn't try hard enough.	4.10	High Motivation	3.80	High Motivation
26. I like the subject matter of this course.	3.34	High Motivation	4.46	Very High Motivation
27. Understanding the subject matter of this course is very important to me.	4.24	Very High Motivation	4.29	Very High Motivation
28. I feel my heart beating fast when I take an exam.	3.76	High Motivation	4.171	High Motivation
29. I'm certain I can master the skills being taught in this class.	3.83	High Motivation	4.098	High Motivation
30. I want to do well in this class because it is important to show my ability to my family, friends, employers, or others.	4.22	Very High Motivation	4.024	High Motivation

31. Considering the difficulty of this course, the teacher, and my skills, I think I will do well in this class.	4.32	Very High Motivation	4.220	Very High Motivation
Overall Motivation	4.00	High Motivation	4.286	Very High Motivation

Legend:

4.21-5.00	Very High Motivation
3.41-4.20	High Motivation
2.61-3.40	Average Motivation
1.81-2.60	Low Motivation
1.01- 1.80	Very Low Motivation

Table 14 shows the students' motivation levels before and after training with the created video-assisted instructional materials. The indicators are categorized based on various motivational elements that influence students' learning behavior, including intrinsic motivation, study tactics, learning beliefs, performance comparison, and external incentives. The pre-test and post-test scores are presented, along with the mean and descriptive interpretation.

The table indicates an increase in students' motivation levels before and after training with the developed video-assisted instructional materials. Overall, students exhibited high motivation levels before instruction, with a mean score of 4.00, interpreted as "High Motivation." Following the instruction, there was a notable improvement in motivation levels, with a mean score of 4.286, interpreted as "Very High Motivation." Specific indicators, such as a preference for challenging course material, belief in learning outcomes, a focus on understanding over grades, and confidence in academic abilities, all saw significant increases.

Furthermore, video-assisted instruction can significantly enhance student motivation by making learning more engaging and accessible. By incorporating videos, teachers can create a dynamic and interactive learning environment that fosters student motivation. Videos provide a visual and accessible introduction to concepts, helping students develop a better understanding of mathematical principles, build confidence in their abilities, and ultimately achieve greater success in their studies.

The results on student motivation levels, before and after the implementation of video-assisted instruction, was supported by the study of Dang et al. (2021). This research emphasizes the significant influence of student characteristics, particularly motivation, on mathematical achievement. The observed increase in student motivation following the video-assisted instruction directly supports these findings, suggesting that interventions designed to enhance motivation can positively impact mathematical outcomes.

In conclusion, video-assisted instruction proved crucial in enhancing students' motivation in mathematics. By utilizing video lessons, students were able to actively participate and gain a deeper understanding of the subject. This resulted in a significant improvement in their motivation, as evidenced by the increased mean score on the post-test.

3.3 Anxiety Level of the Students Before and After Instruction Using the Developed Video-Assisted Instruction

Table 15

Anxiety Level of the Students Before and After Instruction Using the Developed Video-Assisted Instruction

Indicators	Mean	Before Descriptive Interpretation	Mean	After Descriptive Interpretation
1. Feeling happy for not being called to answer questions in class	2.90	Average Anxiety	2.83	Average Anxiety
2. The math section of standardized tests triggers a feeling of panic in me.	3.22	Average Anxiety	2.68	Average Anxiety
3. I hesitate to ask questions in math class when I don't understand something.	3.02	Average Anxiety	2.88	Average Anxiety
4. I find math homework to be a dreaded task.	2.46	Low Anxiety	2.49	Low Anxiety
5. Equations in science courses are not something I enjoy working with.	2.54	Low Anxiety	2.54	Low Anxiety
6. A large amount of math homework makes me feel overwhelmed and anxious.	2.93	Average Anxiety	2.73	Average Anxiety
7. Holding a math textbook to study often makes me feel physically uncomfortable, like a stomachache.	3.07	Average Anxiety	2.56	Low Anxiety
8. It's difficult for me to focus on anything else before a math exam.	3.32	Average Anxiety	3.12	Average Anxiety
9. I dislike being the treasurer of school clubs because it involves dealing with numbers.	2.88	Average Anxiety	2.73	Average Anxiety
10. I experience anxiety when I think about my math grade.	3.29	Average Anxiety	3.22	Average Anxiety
11. Presenting problems I can solve to the teacher makes me feel uneasy.	3.59	High Anxiety	3.05	Average Anxiety
12. I avoid helping children with their math homework because I'm afraid of encountering a problem I can't solve.	3.02	Average Anxiety	3.02	Average Anxiety
13. The thought of a math pop-quiz fills me with apprehension.	3.07	Average Anxiety	2.73	Average Anxiety
14. I tend to arrive late on the first day of math classes every year.	2.20	Low Anxiety	2.59	Low Anxiety
15. My worry about my grade makes it difficult for me to study effectively for math exams.	3.32	Average Anxiety	2.68	Average Anxiety
16. Opening my math book and seeing the pages makes me fear that I will fail the course.	3.20	Average Anxiety	3.22	Average Anxiety
17. I avoid asking my teacher for clarification on math concepts I don't understand.	2.63	Average Anxiety	2.63	Average Anxiety
18. Waiting for the results of a math exam makes me feel anxious and pessimistic.	3.32	Average Anxiety	3.15	Average Anxiety

19. I prefer learning subjects presented with numbers or graphics rather than solely through words.	3.24	Average Anxiety	3.20	Average Anxiety
20. The thought of the math requirements for completing my schoolwork feels overwhelming.	3.29	Average Anxiety	2.98	Average Anxiety
21. I generally dislike working with numbers.	2.61	Low Anxiety	2.61	Low Anxiety
22. I feel self-conscious when my friends notice that I don't understand a math solution.	3.12	Average Anxiety	3.07	Average Anxiety
23. I struggle to pay attention to my math teachers.	3.07	Average Anxiety	2.46	Low Anxiety
24. The parts of other courses that involve mathematics are the most challenging for me.	3.10	Average Anxiety	2.85	Average Anxiety
25. Learning that the next lesson is mathematics makes me feel nervous.	3.39	Average Anxiety	2.51	Low Anxiety
26. I don't enjoy making calculations in everyday life.	2.54	Low Anxiety	2.63	Average Anxiety
27. I often find myself misunderstanding concepts in math courses.	2.98	Average Anxiety	2.85	Average Anxiety
28. I panic when I can't remember the necessary equation for a problem.	3.34	Average Anxiety	3.32	Average Anxiety
29. I dislike browsing through mathematics books.	2.41	Low Anxiety	2.34	Low Anxiety
30. Even if I suspect a salesman has made a mistake with my bill, I hesitate to question it because I'm afraid of being unable to make the calculations in front of others.	3.15	Average Anxiety	3.00	Average Anxiety
Overall Anxiety Level	3.07	Average Anxiety	2.82	Average Anxiety

Legend:

4.21-5.00	Very High Anxiety
3.41-4.20	High Anxiety
2.61-3.40	Average Anxiety
1.81-2.60	Low Anxiety
1.01- 1.80	Very Low Anxiety

Table 15 presents the anxiety levels of students before and after using video-assisted instructional materials. Prior to the implementation of video-assisted instruction, students exhibited a wide range of anxiety levels across different aspects of mathematics. The average anxiety level before instruction was 3.07, classified as "average anxiety." While some indicators, such as *finding math homework a dreaded task* or *disliking the role of treasurer due to its numerical nature*, suggested low anxiety levels, others, such as *feeling uneasy when presenting solved problems to the teacher* or *experiencing anxiety about math grades*, indicated higher levels of anxiety. This suggests that the students already had pre-existing anxieties surrounding mathematics, with certain aspects triggering more anxiety than others.

Following the introduction of video-assisted instructional materials, the average anxiety level decreased slightly to 2.82, remaining within the "average anxiety" category. While this suggests an overall reduction in anxiety levels, notable fluctuations emerged

across different indicators. Some indicators, such as *feeling physically uncomfortable when studying math or struggling to pay attention in math class*, showed a decrease in anxiety levels. This could indicate that the video-assisted materials helped address specific anxieties related to studying and classroom engagement. However, other indicators, such as *feeling nervous about upcoming math lessons or panicking when unable to recall equations*, showed consistent or slightly increased anxiety levels. This suggests that the intervention may have had a mixed impact on different anxieties, potentially alleviating some while exacerbating others.

The results on students' anxiety levels, when considered in the context of the study by Appiah Essuman, Nyarko, and Frimpong (2021), support the idea that addressing mathematics anxiety can lead to improved performance. The use of innovative instructional methods, such as the video-assisted instruction, can contribute to reducing anxiety levels and creating a more conducive learning environment for learners'.

In conclusion, the developed Video-Assisted Instructional Materials had a positive impact on reducing students' anxiety related to mathematics and related tasks.

3.4 Students' Attitude Before and After Instruction Using the Developed Video-assisted Instruction

Table 16

Students' Attitude Before and After Instruction Using the Developed Video-assisted Instruction

Indicators	Before		After	
	Mean	DI	Mean	DI
1. Mathematics is a subject I am afraid of.	3.34	AM	2.46	LM
2. When I work with problems in Mathematics, my thinking and reasoning are sharpened.	2.98	AM	3.37	AM
3. I am unable to think clearly when working with Mathematics.	3.02	AM	2.71	AM
4. I feel excited learning about Mathematics.	2.78	AM	3.80	HM
5. Study of Mathematics is not important unless you are an engineer.	2.37	LM	2.10	LM
6. Learning Mathematics makes me feel bored.	2.34	LM	2.37	LM
7. I feel bored listening to people talking about Mathematics	2.66	AM	2.61	LM
8. Mathematics is a topic I greatly enjoy.	3.49	HM	3.56	HM
9. Of all my teachers, I like Mathematics teacher least.	3.46	HM	3.59	HM
10. Being with people who are good at Mathematics is enjoyable	3.54	HM	3.63	HM
11. No matter how hard I try, I cannot understand Mathematics	3.00	AM	2.85	AM
12. I feel happier in my Mathematics class than in any other class.	2.71	AM	3.32	AM
13. Mathematics gives me such satisfaction	3.10	AM	3.27	AM

14. Mathematics is not necessary in our country.	2.71	AM	2.15	LM
15. I find Mathematics useful for problems of everyday life.	3.49	HM	3.78	HM
16. I don't enjoy going beyond the assigned work in Mathematics.	2.90	AM	2.24	LM
17. I feel I have a good foundation in Mathematics.	3.02	AM	3.51	HM
18. I study Mathematics just to pass the year level.	2.95	AM	2.37	LM
19. I feel nervous in Mathematics class.	3.17	AM	2.54	LM
20. I have a feeling I can get a high grade in Mathematics.	3.15	AM	2.78	AM
21. I feel uncomfortable listening to Mathematics.	2.93	AM	2.83	AM
22. I would not enjoy working with Mathematics.	2.44	LM	2.73	AM
23. Learning Mathematics makes me feel great	3.20	AM	3.71	HM
24. Being with people who are good in Mathematics is boring.	2.63	AM	2.29	LM
25. I am confident when solving Mathematics problems.	3.46	HM	3.39	AM
Overall Attitude	2.99	AM	2.96	AM

Legend:

4.21-5.00	Very High Morale (VHM)
3.41-4.20	High Morale (HM)
2.61-3.40	Average Morale (AM)
1.81-2.60	Low Morale (LM)
1.01- 1.80	Very Low Morale (VLM)
DI	Descriptive Interpretation

The table above compares students' attitudes toward mathematics before and after instruction using video-assisted instructional materials. Before the intervention, the overall attitude score was 2.99, classified as "Morale is Average." After utilizing video-assisted instruction, the overall attitude score was 2.96, also classified as "Morale is Average." Despite a slight decrease in the overall score, the results suggest a positive shift in students' attitudes toward mathematics following the instruction. A significant improvement was observed in several cases, with morale moving from average to high. *Students reported feeling less apprehensive about mathematics and more confident in their problem-solving abilities.* The majority of *students recognized the importance and practicality of mathematics in everyday life.* While some students still harbored reservations about specific aspects of mathematics, the overall trend points to a positive change in attitudes.

The study by Casmir et al. (2019) provides a valuable framework for understanding the potential impact of video-assisted instruction on students' attitudes towards mathematics. In response, using video-assisted instruction could be a valuable tool for maintaining or even enhancing students' positive attitudes as they progress through their education.

In addition, the study on "Secondary school students' attitude towards mathematics word problems" (2022) suggests that fostering early math interest,

employing varied classroom practices, and providing continuous professional development for teachers are crucial factors in shaping students' attitudes towards mathematics. The video-assisted instruction employed in the study serves as a potential example of a varied classroom practice that can contribute to positive attitude shifts, particularly when implemented effectively by well-trained teachers.

In conclusion, the use of video-assisted instruction in mathematics appears to positively influence students' attitudes towards the subject, as supported by research by Huang et al. (2020), which found that video-based instruction enhances achievement, promotes positive attitudes, and reduces anxiety.

Part IV. Level of Mathematical Skills of the Learners Before and After Using the Video-Assisted Instructions.

Table 17

Level of Mathematical Skills of the Learners Before and After Using Video-Assisted Instructions.

Most Essential Learning Competencies in Mathematics 8 Quarter 2	Before		After		Difference (Posttest-Pretest)
	Mean Percentage Score	Descriptive Interpretation	Mean Percentage Score	Descriptive Interpretation	
1. Illustrating a relation and a function	35.12	Average	61.95	Average	26.83
2. Verifying if a given relation is a function	17.07	Low	47.56	Average	30.49
3. Determining dependent and independent variable	48.78	Average	63.41	Average	14.63
4. Finding the domain and range of a function	29.27	Low	63.41	Average	34.14
5. Determining the relationship between the hypothesis and the conclusion of an If- then statement	26.34	Low	45.37	Average	19.03
6. Transforming a statement into an equivalent if-then statement	22.93	Low	35.61	Average	9.27
7. Determining the inverse, converse, and	25.20	Low	35.00	Average	9.80

contrapositive of an if-then statement					
Overall Mathematical Skills	27.97	Low	50.33	Average	22.36

Legend:

96-100	Mastered
86-95	Closely Approximating Mastery
66-85	Moving Towards Mastery
35-65	Average
15-34	Low
5-14	Very low
0-4	Absolutely No Mastery

Table 17 presents a comparison of Grade 8 students' mathematics performance before and after the implementation of video-assisted instruction, focusing on specific learning competencies. The competencies are categorized based on those least mastered by the students. The table includes pre-test and post-test scores, as well as the Mean Percentage Score (MPS) and a descriptive interpretation to classify student performance between the two assessments.

Table 17 indicates an improvement in the performance of Grade 8 students in various mathematical competencies after implementing video-assisted instructions. The mean percentage score on the post-test shows an improvement compared to the pre-test. In *illustrating a relation and a function*, the mean percentage score increased from 35.12% (Average) before to 61.95% (Average) after, showing substantial growth of 26.83 points. Similarly, *verifying if a given relation is a function* showed a notable improvement in this competency, with the mean percentage score rising from 17.07% (Low) to 47.56% (Average), reflecting an increase of 30.49 points. *Determining dependent and independent variables*, learners showed improvement in this area, with the mean percentage score increasing from 48.78% (Average) to 63.41% (Average), indicating a rise of 14.63 points. *Finding the domain and range of a function* has significant progress was observed, with the mean percentage score advancing from 29.27 (Low) to 63.41 (Average), indicating an improvement of 34.14 points. *Determining the relationship between the hypothesis and conclusion of an if-then statement*, learners demonstrated enhancement in this skill, with the mean percentage score increasing from 26.34 (Low) to 45.37 (Average), showing a growth of 19.03 points. *Transforming a statement into an equivalent if-then statement* shows an improvement in this competency, with the mean percentage score increasing from 22.93 (Low) to 35.61 (Average), indicating a rise of 9.27 points. *Determining the inverse, converse, and contrapositive of an if-then statement*, learners showed progress in this area, with the mean percentage score increasing from 25.20 (Low) to 35.00 (Average), reflecting an increase of 9.80 points. Overall, the learners' mathematical skills significantly improved, as seen in the Overall Mathematical Skills score increased from 27.97 (Low) before to 50.33 (Average) after, showing an overall improvement of 22.36 points. This data indicates the effectiveness of video-assisted Instruction in enhancing learners' mathematical competencies across various areas. Despite these improvements, the learners still did not meet the expected

standards of 80%, suggesting the need for further interventions to enhance their mathematical abilities.

The study by Oco and Sabasaje (2023) emphasizes the importance of developing mathematical skills and teacher training. The results of study, by demonstrating significant improvements in mathematical skills after video-assisted instruction, provides empirical evidence supporting these recommendations. This highlights the potential of video-assisted instruction, when implemented effectively by well-trained teachers, to enhance students' mathematical abilities.

Furthermore, the research by Huang et al. (2020) provides strong support for the findings in the study, suggesting that video-assisted instruction can be a valuable tool for enhancing mathematics achievement, promoting positive attitudes, and reducing anxiety. These highlight the potential of video-assisted instruction to create a more engaging and effective learning environment, ultimately contributing to improved mathematical skills and a more positive attitude towards mathematics.

Despite these positive developments, the learners still did not meet the expected standards of 80% according to the evaluation criteria. This suggests that while video-assisted instruction was beneficial in improving mathematical skills, additional support or adjustments may be necessary to bridge the gap between current skill levels and desired expectations. Further interventions could include targeted remedial sessions, personalized learning approaches, or reinforcement activities to solidify the knowledge gained from the video-assisted instruction. By addressing these areas and tailoring instructional strategies to individual learning needs, learners may be better equipped to meet the expected standards and further enhance their mathematical skills.

Part V. Significant Difference in Learners' Behavior Before and After Using the Video-Assisted Instruction

Table 18

Paired Sample Test Results in learners' Motivation before and after using the Video-Assisted Instruction

Statement	Paired Sample Test							
	Mean	Paired Differences			t	df	p-value	
		Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	Interval of the Lower Upper				
1. In a class like this, I prefer course material that really challenges me so I can learn new things.	.463	2.05	.32	-.18	1.11	1.45	40	.156
2. If I study in appropriate ways, then I will be able to learn the material in this course.	.659	2.38	.37	-.09	1.41	1.77	40	.084
3. When I take a test, I think about how poorly I am	.585	2.31	.36	-.14	1.32	1.62	40	.113

	doing compared with other students.								
4.	I think I will be able to use what I learn in this course in other courses.	.780	1.74	.27	.23	1.33	2.87	40	.006
5.	I believe I will receive an excellent grade in this class.	.024	2.32	.36	-.71	0.76	0.07	40	.947
6.	I'm certain I can understand the most difficult material presented in the readings for this course.	.122	1.98	.31	-.50	0.75	0.39	40	.695
7.	Getting a good grade in this class is the most satisfying thing for me right now.	.220	2.40	.38	-.54	0.98	0.58	40	.562
8.	When I take a test I think about items on other parts of the test I can't answer.	-.268	1.87	.29	-.86	0.32	-0.92	40	.364
9.	It is my own fault if I don't learn the material in this course.	.585	2.42	.38	-.18	1.35	1.55	40	.129
10.	It is important for me to learn the course material in this class.	.073	2.40	.38	-.68	0.83	0.20	40	.846
11.	The most important thing for me right now is improving my overall grade point average, so my main concern in this class is getting a good grade.	.780	2.52	.39	-.02	1.58	1.98	40	.055
12.	I'm confident I can learn the basic concepts taught in this course.	.146	2.17	.34	-.54	0.83	0.43	40	.669
13.	If I can, I want to get better grades in this class than most of the other students.	.341	2.36	.37	-.40	1.09	0.93	40	.360
14.	When I take tests I think of the consequences of failing.	-.049	2.47	.39	-.83	0.73	-0.13	40	.900
15.	I'm confident I can understand the most complex material presented by the instructor in this course.	.024	2.19	.34	-.67	0.71	0.07	40	.943
16.	In a class like this, I prefer course material that arouses my curiosity, even if it is difficult to learn.	.585	2.41	.38	-.17	1.35	1.56	40	.127
17.	I am very interested in the content area of this course.	.756	2.00	.31	.13	1.39	2.42	40	.020
18.	If I try hard enough, then I will understand the course material.	.195	1.85	.29	-.39	0.78	0.68	40	.503
19.	I have an uneasy, upset feeling when I take an exam.	-.049	2.20	.34	-.74	0.65	-0.14	40	.888

20. I'm confident I can do an excellent job on the assignments and tests in this course.	.415	2.32	.36	-.32	1.15	1.14	40	.260
21. I expect to do well in this class.	.317	2.45	.38	-.46	1.09	0.83	40	.413
22. The most satisfying thing for me in this course is trying to understand the content as thoroughly as possible.	.317	2.26	.35	-.40	1.03	0.90	40	.375
23. I think the course material in this class is useful for me to learn.	.293	2.17	.34	-.39	0.98	0.86	40	.393
24. When I have the opportunity in this class, I choose course assignments that I can learn from even if they don't guarantee a good grade.	.195	2.25	.35	-.51	0.91	0.56	40	.582
25. If I don't understand the course material, it is because I didn't try hard enough.	-.293	2.62	.41	-1.12	0.53	-0.72	40	.479
26. I like the subject matter of this course.	1.12	1.96	.31	.50	1.74	3.66	40	.001
27. Understanding the subject matter of this course is very important to me.	.049	2.05	.32	-.60	0.70	0.15	40	.880
28. I feel my heart beating fast when I take an exam.	.415	1.87	.29	-.18	1.01	1.42	40	.164
29. I'm certain I can master the skills being taught in this class.	.268	2.01	.31	-.37	0.90	0.85	40	.398
30. I want to do well in this class because it is important to show my ability to my family, friends, employer, or others.	-.195	2.37	.37	-.94	0.55	-0.53	40	.601
31. Considering the difficulty of this course, the teacher, and my skills, I think I will do well in this class.	-.098	2.00	.31	-.73	0.53	-0.31	40	.756
Average Motivation	.463	1.00	.16	-.03	0.60	1.81	40	.077

Table 18 shows the results from the paired samples t-test on students' motivation before and after the implementation of video-assisted instructional materials, indicating whether there is a significant difference between the two sets of scores from post-test to pre-test.

The statement "I think I will be able to use what I learn in this course in other courses" showed a significant improvement from the post-test compared to the pre-test, with a mean difference of 0.780, a standard deviation of 1.74, and a standard error of 0.27. The 95% confidence interval lies between 0.23 and 1.33, meaning we are 95% confident that the true difference in means falls within this range. The t-value is 2.87 with

40 degrees of freedom ($df = 40$), and the p-value is 0.006, which is highly significant ($p < 0.001$). This suggests that learners feel more confident about applying their course learnings in other contexts after using the video-based materials. For the statement "I am very interested in the content area of this course," scores after using the intervention (post-test) showed a statistically significant improvement compared to the pre-test scores, with a mean difference of 0.756, a standard deviation of 2.00, and a standard error of 0.31. The 95% confidence interval lies between 0.13 and 1.39, meaning we are 95% confident that the true difference in means falls within this range. The t-value is 2.42 with 40 degrees of freedom ($df = 40$), and the p-value is 0.020, which is highly significant ($p < 0.05$), indicating that learners' interest in the course content has increased notably after engaging with the video-based materials. Another statement, "I like the subject matter of this course," falls within a mean difference of 1.12, a standard deviation of 1.96, and a standard error of 0.31. The 95% confidence interval lies between 0.50 and 1.74, meaning we are 95% confident that the true difference in means falls within this range. The t-value is 3.66 with 40 degrees of freedom ($df = 40$), and the p-value is 0.001, which is highly significant ($p < 0.05$). This suggests that learners' preference for the course subject matter has significantly improved following the use of video-based materials. Other statements, such as "In a class like this, I prefer course material that really challenges me so I can learn new things," "If I study in appropriate ways, then I will be able to learn the material in this course," "When I take a test, I think about how poorly I am doing compared with other students," "I believe I will receive an excellent grade in this class," "I'm certain I can understand the most difficult material presented in the readings for this course," "Getting a good grade in this class is the most satisfying thing for me right now," "When I take a test I think about items on other parts of the test I can't answer," "It is my own fault if I don't learn the material in this course," "It is important for me to learn the course material in this class," "The most important thing for me right now is improving my overall grade point average, so my main concern in this class is getting a good grade," "I'm confident I can learn the basic concepts taught in this course," "If I can, I want to get better grades in this class than most of the other students," "When I take tests I think of the consequences of failing," "I'm confident I can understand the most complex material presented by the instructor in this course," "In a class like this, I prefer course material that arouses my curiosity, even if it is difficult to learn," "If I try hard enough, then I will understand the course material," "I have an uneasy, upset feeling when I take an exam," "I'm confident I can do an excellent job on the assignments and tests in this course," "I expect to do well in this class," "The most satisfying thing for me in this course is trying to understand the content as thoroughly as possible," "I think the course material in this class is useful for me to learn," "When I have the opportunity in this class, I choose course assignments that I can learn from even if they don't guarantee a good grade," "If I don't understand the course material, it is because I didn't try hard enough," "Understanding the subject matter of this course is very important to me," "I feel my heart beating fast when I take an exam," "I'm certain I can master the skills being taught in this class," "I want to do well in this class because it is important to show my ability to my family, friends, employer, or others," and "Considering the difficulty of this course, the teacher, and my skills, I think I will do well in this class," were not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$). However, the mean differences in motivation scores between the pre-test and post-test were positive, indicating an increase in motivation levels after the utilization of video-

assisted instructional materials. The overall average motivation showed a positive mean difference of 0.28, but the p-value of 0.077 shows that this difference is not statistically significant at the standard significance level of 0.05.

Research by Dang et.al (2021) found that student characteristics, such as interest, motivation, and self-efficacy, significantly impact mathematical achievement, with self-efficacy having the most substantial influence. The use of video-assisted instruction in Mathematics 8 may have influenced learners' motivation to increase in learning mathematics.

In conclusion, the results indicate that the use of Video-Assisted Instruction in Mathematics 8 increased learners' motivation, particularly in areas such as the perceived usefulness of course material, interest in the content, and enjoyment of the subject matter. However, further research and examination of individual statements may provide more insight into the specific motivational characteristics that were positively impacted by the intervention.

Table 19
Paired Sample Test Results on learners' Anxiety before and after using the Video-Assisted Instruction

Statement	Mean	Paired Differences		Interval of the		t	df	p-value
		Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	Lower	Upper			
1. Feeling happy for not being called to answer questions in class	-.073	1.47	.23	-.54	.39	-.32	40	.75
2. The math section of standardized tests triggers a feeling of panic in me.	-.537	1.47	.23	-1.00	-.07	-2.34	40	.02
3. I hesitate to ask questions in math class when I don't understand something.	-.146	1.57	.25	-.64	.35	-.60	40	.56
4. I find math homework to be a dreaded task.	.024	1.56	.24	-.47	.52	.10	40	.92
5. Equations in science courses are not something I enjoy working with.	.000	1.32	.21	-.42	.42	.00	40	1.00
6. A large amount of math homework makes me feel overwhelmed and anxious.	-.195	1.40	.22	-.64	.25	-.89	40	.38
7. Holding a math textbook to study often makes me feel physically	-.512	1.36	.21	-.94	-.08	-2.41	40	.02

uncomfortable, like a stomachache.									
8. It's difficult for me to focus on anything else before a math exam.	-.195	1.65	.26	-.71	.32	-.76	40	.45	
9. I dislike being the treasurer of school clubs because it involves dealing with numbers.	-.146	1.81	.28	-.72	.43	-.52	40	.61	
10. I experience anxiety when I think about my math grade.	-.073	1.39	.22	-.51	.36	-.34	40	.74	
11. Presenting problems I can solve to the teacher makes me feel uneasy.	-.537	1.60	.25	-1.04	-.03	-2.15	40	.04	
12. I avoid helping children with their math homework because I'm afraid of encountering a problem I can't solve.	.000	1.84	.29	-.58	.58	.00	40	1.00	
13. The thought of a math pop-quiz fills me with apprehension.	-.341	1.48	.23	-.81	.12	-1.48	40	.15	
14. I tend to arrive late on the first day of math classes every year.	.390	1.72	.27	-.15	.93	1.46	40	.15	
15. My worry about my grade makes it difficult for me to study effectively for math exams.	-.634	1.53	.24	-1.12	-.15	-2.66	40	.01	
16. Opening my math book and seeing the pages makes me fear that I will fail the course.	.024	1.59	.25	-.48	.53	.10	40	.92	
17. I avoid asking my teacher for clarification on math concepts I don't understand.	.000	1.18	.18	-.37	.37	.00	40	1.00	
18. Waiting for the results of a math exam makes me feel anxious and pessimistic.	-.171	1.28	.20	-.58	.23	-.85	40	.40	
19. I prefer learning subjects presented with numbers or graphics rather than solely through words.	-.049	1.30	.20	-.46	.36	-.24	40	.81	
20. The thought of the math requirements for completing my schoolwork feels overwhelming.	-.317	1.79	.28	-.88	.25	-1.13	40	.26	
21. I generally dislike working with numbers.	.000	1.41	.22	-.45	.45	.00	40	1.00	

22. I feel self-conscious when my friends notice that I don't understand a math solution.	-.049	1.56	.24	-.54	.45	-.20	40	.84
23. I struggle to pay attention to my math teachers.	-.610	1.46	.23	-1.07	-.15	-2.67	40	.01
24. The parts of other courses that involve mathematics are the most challenging for me.	-.244	1.32	.21	-.66	.17	-1.18	40	.24
25. Learning that the next lesson is mathematics makes me feel nervous.	-.878	1.69	.26	-1.41	-.34	-3.32	40	.00
26. I don't enjoy making calculations in everyday life.	.098	1.37	.21	-.34	.53	.45	40	.65
27. I often find myself misunderstanding concepts in math courses.	-.122	1.27	.20	-.52	.28	-.62	40	.54
28. I panic when I can't remember the necessary equation for a problem.	-.024	1.85	.29	-.61	.56	-.08	40	.93
29. I dislike browsing through mathematics books.	-.073	1.57	.25	-.57	.42	-.30	40	.77
30. Even if I suspect a salesman has made a mistake with my bill, I hesitate to question it because I'm afraid of being unable to make the calculations in front of others.	-.146	1.48	.23	-.61	.32	-.63	40	.53
Average Anxiety	-.185	.47	.07	-.33	-.03	-2.49	40	.02

Table 19 presents the results of learners' anxiety levels before and after using video-assisted instructional materials, revealing significant changes in anxiety levels. The statement "The math section of standardized tests triggers a feeling of panic in me" indicates a significant mean difference of -0.537, with a p-value of 0.02, suggesting that learners experienced a reduction in their feelings of panic when encountering the math section of standardized tests after the implementation of video-assisted instruction.

The statement "Holding a math textbook to study often makes me feel physically uncomfortable, like a stomach ache" had a mean difference of -0.512, a standard deviation of 1.36, and a standard error of 0.21. The 95% confidence interval of the difference lies between -0.94 and -0.08, meaning we are 95% confident that the true difference in means falls within this range. The t-value is -2.41, with 40 degrees of freedom (df = 40), and the p-value is 0.02, which is highly significant ($p < 0.05$). This result

suggests a statistically significant decrease in anxiety levels from the pretest to the posttest.

The statement "Presenting problems I can solve to the teacher makes me feel uneasy" had a mean difference of -0.537, a standard deviation of 1.60, and a standard error of 0.25. The 95% confidence interval lies between -1.04 and -0.03, meaning that the mean difference falls within this range. The t-value is -2.15, with 40 degrees of freedom ($df = 40$), and the p-value is 0.04, which is highly significant ($p < 0.05$). This indicates that students, after the implementation of the intervention, experienced a reduction in their anxiety levels about presenting problems to the teacher.

The statement "My worry about my grade makes it difficult for me to study effectively for math exams" indicates a significant mean difference of -0.634 with a p-value of 0.01, suggesting that learners' worry about their grades significantly reduced, making it easier for them to study effectively for math exams.

The statement "I struggle to pay attention to my math teachers" had a mean difference of -0.610, a standard deviation of 1.46, and a standard error of 0.23, with the 95% confidence interval lying between -1.07 and -0.15. The t-value is -2.65, with 40 degrees of freedom ($df = 40$), and the p-value is 0.01, which is highly significant ($p < 0.05$).

The statement "Learning that the next lesson is mathematics makes me feel nervous" showed a highly significant mean difference of -0.88, with a p-value of 0.00, suggesting that learners, after the implementation of video-assisted instruction, effectively reduced their anxiety levels about feeling nervous when mathematics was the next lesson.

Several statements did not show a statistically significant difference in anxiety levels after the intervention, such as: "Feeling happy for not being called to answer questions in class," "I hesitate to ask questions in math class when I don't understand something," "I find math homework to be a dreaded task," "Equations in science courses are not something I enjoy working with," "A large amount of math homework makes me feel overwhelmed and anxious," "It's difficult for me to focus on anything else before a math exam," "I dislike being the treasurer of school clubs because it involves dealing with numbers," "I experience anxiety when I think about my math grade," "I avoid helping children with their math homework because I'm afraid of encountering a problem I can't solve," "The thought of a math pop-quiz fills me with apprehension," "I tend to arrive late on the first day of math classes every year," "Opening my math book and seeing the pages makes me fear that I will fail the course," "I avoid asking my teacher for clarification on math concepts I don't understand," "Waiting for the results of a math exam makes me feel anxious and pessimistic," "I prefer learning subjects presented with numbers or graphics rather than solely through words," "The thought of the math requirements for completing my schoolwork feels overwhelming," "I generally dislike working with numbers," "I feel self-conscious when my friends notice that I don't understand a math solution," "The parts of other courses that involve mathematics are the most challenging for me," "I don't enjoy making calculations in everyday life," "I often find myself

misunderstanding concepts in math courses," "I panic when I can't remember a necessary equation for a problem," "I dislike browsing through mathematics books," and "Even if I suspect a salesman has made a mistake with my bill, I hesitate to question it because I'm afraid of being unable to make the calculations in front of others." These statements had p-values ($p > 0.05$). The average anxiety decrease was reported as -0.185, with a standard error of 0.07 and a confidence interval of -0.33 to -0.03. The t-value of -2.49 and p-value of 0.02 suggest a statistically significant decrease in anxiety levels on average. Some statements showed considerable improvements in anxiety, whereas others did not. This shows that the effect of video-assisted instructional materials on anxiety may differ depending on the specific element of anxiety.

The study by Yaftian, & Barghamadi, (2022) on "The effect of teaching using multimedia on mathematical anxiety and motivation" found that multimedia systems significantly impacted students' motivation and anxiety levels in mathematics. This supports the observed reduction in anxiety in the study, which could be attributed to the engaging and interactive nature of video-assisted instruction.

In conclusion, the data indicate that the use of Video-Assisted Instructional materials has led to significant reductions in anxiety levels among students, particularly in areas such as panic triggers during standardized tests, discomfort while studying math textbooks, worry about grades, and struggles to pay attention to math teachers. The findings demonstrate the effectiveness of these educational materials in alleviating anxiety in math-related situations.

Table 20
Paired Sample Test Results on Learners' Attitude before and after using the Video-Assisted Instruction

Statement	Paired Sample Test					t	df	p-value
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	Interval of the Lower	Upper			
1. Mathematics is a subject I am afraid of.	-.88	1.60	.25	-1.38	-.37	-3.51	40	.001
2. When I work with problems in Mathematics, my thinking and reasoning are sharpened.	.39	1.39	.22	-.05	.83	1.79	40	.081
3. I am unable to think clearly when working with Mathematics.	-.32	.99	.15	-.63	-.01	-2.06	40	.046
4. I feel excited learning about Mathematics.	1.02	1.31	.21	.61	1.44	5.00	40	.000
5. Study of Mathematics is not important unless you are an engineer.	-.27	1.78	.28	-.83	.29	-.97	40	.339
6. Learning Mathematics makes me feel bored.	.02	1.29	.20	-.38	.43	.12	40	.905

7. I feel bored listening to people taking about Mathematics	-.05	1.40	.22	-.49	.39	-.22	40	.824
8. Mathematics is a topic I greatly enjoy.	.07	1.69	.26	-.46	.61	.28	40	.784
9. Of all my teachers, I like Mathematics teacher least.	.12	1.58	.25	-.38	.62	.49	40	.625
10. Being with people who are good in Mathematics is enjoyable	.10	1.09	.17	-.25	.44	.57	40	.570
11. No matter how hard I try, I cannot understand Mathematics	-.15	1.78	.28	-.71	.42	-.53	40	.602
12. I feel happier in my Mathematics class than in any other class.	.61	1.38	.21	.18	1.04	2.84	40	.007
13. Mathematics gives me such satisfaction	.17	1.26	.20	-.23	.57	.87	40	.392
14. Mathematics is not necessary in our country.	-.56	1.43	.22	-1.01	-.11	-2.51	40	.016
15. I find Mathematics useful for problems of everyday life.	.29	1.54	.24	-.19	.78	1.22	40	.230
16. I don't enjoy going beyond the assigned work in Mathematics.	-.66	1.37	.21	-1.09	-.23	-3.07	40	.004
17. I feel I have a good foundation in Mathematics.	.49	1.57	.24	-.01	.98	1.99	40	.053
18. I study Mathematics just to pass the year level.	-.59	1.36	.21	-1.01	-.16	-2.76	40	.009
19. I feel nervous in Mathematics class.	-.63	1.43	.22	-1.08	-.18	-2.84	40	.007
20. I have a feeling I can get high grade in Mathematics.	-.37	1.68	.26	-.90	.17	-1.39	40	.172
21. I feel uncomfortable listening to Mathematics.	-.10	1.22	.19	-.48	.29	-.51	40	.612
22. I would not enjoy working with Mathematics.	.29	1.54	.24	-.19	.78	1.22	40	.230
23. Learning Mathematics makes me feel great	.51	1.25	.19	.12	.91	2.63	40	.012
24. Being with people who are good in Mathematics is boring.	-.34	1.35	.21	-.77	.09	-1.62	40	.114
25. I am confident when solving Mathematics problems.	-.07	1.23	.19	-.46	.32	-.38	40	.706
Average Attitude	-.04	.47	.07	-.18	.11	-.47	40	.638

Table 20 presents the results of learners' attitudes toward mathematics before and after using video-assisted instructional materials, suggesting a considerable impact on their attitudes.

The statement "Mathematics is a subject I am afraid of" had a mean difference of -0.88, a standard deviation of 1.60, and a standard error of 0.25. The 95% confidence interval lies between -1.38 and -0.37, meaning we are 95% confident that the true difference in means falls within this range. The t-value is -3.51 with 40 degrees of freedom ($df = 40$), and the p-value is 0.001, which is highly significant ($p < 0.001$). This result suggests a statistically significant improvement in students' attitudes after the implementation of Video-Assisted Instruction in Mathematics 8.

The statement "I am unable to think clearly when working with mathematics" had a positive and significant mean difference of -0.32 from the post-test to pre-test scores after using the intervention, with a standard deviation of 0.99 and a standard error of 0.15. The 95% confidence interval lies between -0.63 and -0.01. The t-value is -2.6, and the p-value is 0.046, indicating that learners were able to think more clearly when working with mathematics.

The statement "I feel excited learning about mathematics" indicates a significant mean difference of 1.02 with a p-value of 0.00, suggesting that learners felt more excited about learning mathematics, leading to a positive change in their attitude.

There was positive improvement in the attitude toward mathematics for the statement "I feel happier in my mathematics class than in any other class," with a mean difference of 0.61, a standard deviation of 1.38, and a standard error of 0.21. The 95% confidence interval lies between 0.18 and 1.04. The t-value is 2.84 with 40 degrees of freedom ($df = 40$), and the p-value is 0.007, which is highly significant ($p < 0.05$).

For the statement "Mathematics is not necessary in our country," the mean difference was -0.56, the standard deviation was 1.43, and the standard error was 0.22. The confidence interval ranged from -1.01 to 0.11. The t-value was -2.51 with a p-value of 0.016, indicating that students perceived mathematics as necessary in our country, leading to a positive change in their behaviour.

The statement "I don't enjoy going beyond the assigned work in mathematics" had a mean difference of -0.66, a standard deviation of 1.37, and a standard error of 0.21. The 95% confidence interval lies between -1.09 and -0.23, meaning we are 95% confident that the true difference in means falls within this range. The t-value is -3.07, with a p-value of 0.004. This indicates that after the intervention, students had a more positive attitude towards going beyond the assigned work in mathematics.

The statement "I study mathematics just to pass the year level" had a mean difference of -0.59, a standard deviation of 1.36, and a standard error of 0.21. The confidence interval ranged from -1.01 to -0.16. The t-value was -2.76 with a p-value of

0.009, suggesting a significant improvement in students' attitudes after using video-assisted instruction.

The statement "I feel nervous in mathematics class" had a mean difference of -0.63, a standard deviation of 1.43, and a standard error of 0.22. The 95% confidence interval lies between -1.08 and -0.18, meaning we are 95% confident that the true difference in means falls within this range. The t-value is -2.84, with 40 degrees of freedom (df = 40), and the p-value is 0.007, which is highly significant ($p < 0.05$). This result suggests a statistically significant improvement in students' attitudes after implementing the intervention.

Some statements showed considerable improvements in positive attitudes, while others did not. This suggests that the impact of video-based resources on learners' attitudes toward mathematics may vary depending on specific attitude components.

Casmir et al. (2019) found that students initially hold positive attitudes towards mathematics, but these attitudes tend to decline as they progress through higher education, often due to ineffective teaching strategies and instructions. Integrating video-assisted instruction in Mathematics 8 may have helped learners increase their positive attitude towards learning mathematics.

In conclusion, the data indicate that the use of Video-Assisted Instructional materials resulted in significant positive improvements in learners' attitudes toward mathematics in key areas. While the average change in attitude may not be statistically significant, increases in enthusiasm, confidence, understanding, and satisfaction with mathematics demonstrate the educational materials' positive impact on learners' perceptions of the subject.

Part VI. Significant Difference in the Mathematical Skills of the Learners Before and After Using the Video-Assisted Instruction

Table 21

Statistical Table Showing the Difference in the Mathematical Skills of the Learners' before and after using the Video-Assisted Instruction

MELCs in Mathematics 8 Quarter 2	Paired Samples Test							
	Paired Differences					t	df	p-value
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	Interval of the Lower	Upper			
Illustrating a relation and a function	26.83	27.43	4.28	18.17	35.49	6.26	40	.000
Verifying if a given relation is a function	30.49	47.27	7.38	15.57	45.41	4.13	40	.000
Determining dependent and independent variable	14.63	61.49	9.60	-4.77	34.04	1.52	40	.135

Finding the domain and range of a function	34.15	54.13	8.45	17.06	51.23	4.04	40	.000
Determining the relationship between the hypothesis and the conclusion of an If-then statement	19.02	30.64	4.79	9.35	28.70	3.98	40	.000
Transforming a statement into an equivalent if-then statement	12.68	23.56	3.68	5.25	20.12	3.45	40	.001
Determining the inverse, converse, and contrapositive of an if-then statement	9.76	27.69	4.32	1.02	18.50	2.26	40	.030
Overall Mathematical Skills	17.97	17.78	2.78	12.36	23.58	6.47	40	.000

Table 21 presents the results of the assessments before and after the implementation of Video-Assisted Instruction. A paired sample t-test was used to evaluate whether the mean difference between the two sets of observations is zero.

Table above shows the differences between post-test and pre-test scores for various mathematical competencies, suggesting significant improvements in student performance. For "Illustrating a relation and functions," the mean difference was 26.83, with a standard deviation of 27.43 and a standard error of 4.28. The 95% confidence interval lies between 18.17 and 35.49, meaning we are 95% confident that the true difference in means falls within this range. The t-value is 6.26, with 40 degrees of freedom ($df = 40$), and the p-value is 0.000, which is highly significant ($p < 0.001$). This result suggests a statistically significant increase in scores from the pre-test to the post-test. For "Verifying if a given relation is a function," the mean difference was 30.49, with a standard deviation of 47.27 and a standard error of 7.38. The 95% confidence interval lies between 15.57 and 45.41, meaning we are 95% confident that the true difference in means falls within this range. The t-value is 4.13, with 40 degrees of freedom ($df = 40$), and the p-value is 0.000, which is highly significant ($p < 0.001$). This result suggests a statistically significant increase in scores from the pre-test to the post-test.

For "Determining dependent and independent variables," the mean difference was 14.63, with a standard deviation of 61.49 and a standard error of 9.60. The 95% confidence interval lies between -4.77 and 34.04. The t-value is 1.52, with 40 degrees of freedom ($df = 40$), and the p-value is 0.135, which is not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$). This result suggests that there was no statistically significant difference in scores from the pre-test to the post-test. For "Finding the domain and range of a function," the mean difference was 34.15, with a standard deviation of 54.13 and a standard error of 8.45. The 95% confidence interval lies between 17.14 and 51.16, meaning we are 95% confident that the true difference in means falls within this range. The t-value is 4.04, with 40 degrees of freedom ($df = 40$), and the p-value is 0.000, which is highly significant ($p < 0.001$). This result suggests a statistically significant increase in scores from the pre-test to the post-test. For "Determining the relationship between the hypothesis and the

conclusion of an If-then statement," the mean difference was 19.02, with a standard deviation of 30.64 and a standard error of 4.79. The t-value is 3.98, with 40 degrees of freedom ($df = 40$), and the p-value is 0.000, which is highly significant ($p < 0.001$). This result suggests a statistically significant increase in scores from the pre-test to the post-test. For "Transforming a statement into an equivalent if-then statement," the mean difference was 12.68, with a standard deviation of 23.56 and a standard error of 3.68. The 95% confidence interval lies between 5.25 and 20.12, meaning we are 95% confident that the true difference in means falls within this range. The t-value is 3.45, with 40 degrees of freedom ($df = 40$), and the p-value is 0.001, which is highly significant ($p < 0.001$). This result suggests a statistically significant increase in scores from the pre-test to the post-test. For "Determining the inverse, converse, and contrapositive of an if-then statement," the mean difference was 9.76, with a standard deviation of 27.69 and a standard error of 4.32. The 95% confidence interval lies between 1.02 and 18.50, meaning we are 95% confident that the true difference in means falls within this range. The t-value is 2.26, with 40 degrees of freedom ($df = 40$), and the p-value is 0.030, which is statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). This result suggests a statistically significant increase in scores from the pre-test to the post-test. For "Total mathematical skills," the mean difference was 17.97, with a standard deviation of 17.78 and a standard error of 2.78. The 95% confidence interval lies between 12.36 and 23.50, meaning we are 95% confident that the true difference in means falls within this range. The t-value is 6.47, with 40 degrees of freedom ($df = 40$), and the p-value is 0.000, which is highly significant ($p < 0.001$). This result suggests a statistically significant increase in scores from the pre-test to the post-test.

The study by Insorio et al. (2023) provides strong support for the findings of the study on the difference in learners' mathematical skills before and after using video-assisted instruction, suggesting that video-assisted instruction can be a valuable tool for enhancing mathematical comprehension and performance. This suggests that the use of video-assisted instruction has the potential to create a more engaging and effective learning environment, ultimately contributing to improved mathematical skills.

In conclusion, the data indicate that the video-assisted instruction intervention had a significant positive impact on learners' mathematical skills following its implementation. The results of the t-test provide strong evidence that post-test scores were considerably higher than pre-test scores.

Part VII. Comments and Suggestions Given by the Validators to Improve the Developed Video-Assisted Instruction

The validators' comments and suggestions offer valuable insights for enhancing the effectiveness of video-assisted instruction. Their feedback identifies areas for improvement, providing opportunities to refine the educational approach and create a more impactful learning experience for students.

The validators consistently emphasize the quality of the presentations across the various video lessons developed for Mathematics 8. They commend the lessons for their

clarity and the use of appropriate examples, which make the subject matter easily understandable for students. Teachers effectively engage students by referencing prior teachings, facilitating smooth transitions, and building upon existing knowledge. The use of plain language and proper grammar further enhances comprehension. Additionally, the practice of presenting lesson objectives at the beginning is recognized as beneficial in preparing students for the learning experience.

The validators offer several suggestions for improving video-assisted instruction, focusing on enhancing the visual and auditory experience for learners. They recommend keeping video lessons concise to facilitate better absorption of the material. The font size should be increased to at least 24 points for improved readability, and the number of font styles should be limited to two or three, with Times New Roman, Calibri, and Arial being preferred. Careful consideration of the color scheme is also advised to ensure readability.

The validators also note some technical issues, such as delays in transitions and animations, and suggest addressing these for a smoother viewing experience. Regarding the teacher's voice, they recommend adding variation in modulation to make the delivery more engaging. A conversational tone and pauses for student reflection are also encouraged. Finally, they recommend using appropriate graphics to illustrate examples and including a closing statement for a well-rounded instructional experience.

Berry's (2021) argument about the importance of technology in modern teaching practices provides a strong foundation for the development and validation of the video-assisted instruction. The validators' comments and suggestions, offer valuable insights into how to optimize the video-assisted instruction to effectively engage students and promote learning, ultimately contributing to the broader goal of enhancing educational outcomes.

Part VIII. Enhanced Audio-Visual Material

The Video-Assisted Instruction has emerged as a transformative force in education, leveraging the power of audio-visual media to enhance student engagement and mathematical skills. This approach utilizes video lesson to supplement traditional teaching methods offering a dynamic and interactive learning experience.

This intervention will address the growing least learned competencies and learning gaps in most learning areas in Mathematics 8, unmotivated learners in the teaching-learning process.

The objectives of these intervention are to developed mathematical skills and learners' behavior. The target beneficiaries are those learners' in Bagupaye Integrated High School who are struggling in different areas.

Based on the results presented in the previous parts, the proposed enhanced audio-visual material can be developed. (See Annex A, for the details of enhanced audio-visual material).

DISCUSSION

The study yielded the following findings:

1. The Video-Assisted Instruction Developed

1.1 In terms of content, the video-assisted instruction in Mathematics 8 was designed to help learners' master essential competencies through a structured approach that included objectives, reviews, discussions, examples, activities, and assessments.

1.2 For format and technical design, the researcher incorporated engaging elements like graphics, animations, and real-life examples into the Mathematics 8 video lessons, while ensuring clear audio, background music, and a balanced pace to optimize learner engagement and comprehension.

1.3 In terms of presentation and organization, the bilingual video lesson in Mathematics 8, using Tagalog and English, aimed to improve learning outcomes for diverse students by fostering engagement and reducing anxiety. The lesson's structured flow with smooth transitions prioritized a cohesive learning experience over presenting isolated facts.

1.4 For accuracy and up-to-dateness of information, the researcher thoroughly analyzed the Mathematics 8 video lessons to guarantee correctness and currency, avoiding disinformation or outdated content that could hamper learning, particularly given the lessons' importance in establishing the framework for advanced mathematics studies.

2. The Validity of Video-Assisted Instruction

2.1 In Terms of Content

The video-assisted instructional materials are highly effective regarding content suitability, alignment with learning objectives, and freedom from bias, with mean scores ranging from 3.43 to 3.97. However, there are areas needing improvement in promoting higher cognitive skills such as critical thinking, creativity, and problem-solving, as well as in fostering desirable values, arousing interest, and providing safety and health warnings, with mean scores ranging from 2.89 to 3.09. This indicates that the video-assisted instructional materials have potential for enhancement.

2.2 For Format/Technical Design

There is a positive perception of video-assisted instructional materials, with a weighted mean score of 3.53, reflecting a high level of acceptability. The materials exhibit strong sound quality and volume, effective pacing, and a good balance between information and engagement, with mean scores ranging from 3.83 to 3.86 (High Level of Acceptability). However, there is room for improvement in audio-visual effects, engagement, and safety considerations, as some effects may not be consistently effective, resulting in a mean score of 2.91 (Moderate Level of Acceptability).

2.3 In Terms of Presentation and Organization

There is a high level of acceptability, with a weighted mean score of 3.70 for video-assisted instructional materials, indicating their effectiveness in presentation and organization. The materials are engaging, interesting, and understandable, featuring a logical flow of ideas. The vocabulary used is appropriate and accessible, and the video/audio length is suitable for the target audience's attention span, with mean scores ranging from 3.49 to 3.97. This suggests that the video-assisted instructional materials are well-designed for effective learning.

2.4 For Accuracy and Up-to-dateness of Information

The video-assisted instructional materials exhibit a high level of acceptability, with a weighted mean score of 3.69, demonstrating strengths in factual accuracy, grammatical correctness, computational precision, and current knowledge, with mean scores ranging from 3.51 to 4.00. However, they show moderate acceptability in addressing typographical and minor errors, with a mean score of 2.74, indicating room for improvement to maintain a consistently high standard.

3. Learner Behavior Before, During, and After Instruction Using the Developed Video-Assisted Instruction

3.1 Students' Engagement Behavior During Video Presentations

The data reveals that eighth-grade learners demonstrate consistently strong engagement during video presentations. Students collaborate well with others, complete assigned tasks, approach new assignments with sincere effort, and persist through difficulties. Total mean scores across different videos range from 2.34 to 3.99, with an average mean of 3.27, indicating that students "sometimes" engage in the presentations. However, there is room for improvement in areas where students become discouraged and stop trying when faced with obstacles in schoolwork, as evidenced by a mean score of 1.44, indicating low engagement during these instances.

In terms of initiative, the data shows that students "always" strive to complete their work thoroughly and well, with a total mean score of 4.00 across different videos, reflecting their commitment to quality. They consistently aim for high standards, actively participate in discussions, ask questions for clarification,

and volunteer information, with total mean scores ranging from 3.63 to 3.75, resulting in an average mean of 3.79, indicating that students "sometimes" engage across different video lessons.

The data reveals minimal disruptive behaviors among students, indicating a positive and focused classroom environment. Students maintain focus and composure, rarely exhibiting restlessness or needing reprimands. They respect others' personal space and concentrate on their tasks. Excessive talking with classmates is uncommon, with total mean scores ranging from 1.32 to 1.91 across different video lessons, and the overall average disruptive behavior score ranges from 1.20 to 2.43, indicating a well-maintained and focused classroom.

In terms of inattentive behaviors, the data indicates a focused and engaged classroom environment with minimal inattentiveness among students. Students generally follow classroom activities, show minimal withdrawal or uncommunicative behavior, and rarely require external help, with a total mean across different video lessons ranging from 1.34 to 1.45.

3.2 Students' Motivation Level Before and After Instruction Using the Developed Video-Assisted Instructional Materials

The data reveals that after implementing video-assisted instructional materials, students' mean motivation score increased from 4.00 to 4.286, indicating a shift from "high motivation" to "very high motivation." This positive change suggests that the video-assisted instructional materials effectively improved students' engagement and motivation.

3.3 Students' Anxiety Levels Before and After Instruction Using Developed Video-Assisted Instructional Materials

Before instruction, students demonstrated an overall anxiety level classified as "average anxiety," with a mean score of 3.07. However, after implementing the video-assisted materials, the total anxiety level decreased to "average anxiety," with a mean score of 2.82. This reduction in anxiety indicates that the video-assisted instructional materials may have enhanced students' emotional well-being and comfort levels with the subject matter. The findings suggest that these materials could serve as a useful tool for alleviating anxiety related to studying and potentially improving students' overall learning experiences.

3.4 Students' Attitude Before and After Instruction Using the Developed Video-Assisted Instructional Materials

The data shows that students' attitudes towards mathematics improved slightly after using video-assisted instructional materials, with a marginal decrease from 2.99 to 2.96. However, some indicators remained stable, such as feelings of nervousness in class and a lack of confidence in problem-solving. The study suggests that the instructional materials had a mixed impact on students' attitudes toward mathematics.

4. Learners' Mathematical Skills Before and After Video-Assisted Instruction

The data reveals a slight improvement in mathematical skills, although it is not statistically significant. Before the implementation of the Video-Assisted Instruction, the overall mean percentage score was 27.97, categorized as "Did Not Meet Expectations." After the instruction, the mean percentage score increased to 45.93, still falling under the "Did Not Meet Expectations" category. While this increase indicates some positive impact from the video-assisted instruction, it was insufficient to elevate the learners' mathematical skills to an acceptable level. Further analysis of the video-assisted instruction and the learners' specific needs may be necessary to identify areas for improvement and develop more effective learning strategies to help learners achieve the desired level of mathematical proficiency.

5. Significant Differences in Learners' Behavior Before and After Using the Video-Based Materials

The data reveals significant positive changes in specific aspects of learners' motivation. Statements such as "I believe I will be able to use what I learn in this course in other courses," "I am very interested in the content area of this course," and "I like the subject matter of this course" all showed significance values (p-values) less than 0.05. These results underscore the effectiveness of incorporating video-assisted instructional materials to boost learners' motivation and engagement in the subject matter, ultimately enhancing their overall learning experience. However, some aspects of motivation did not show statistically significant changes, with p-values greater than 0.05, indicating that the learners' motivation levels after the implementation of video-assisted instructional materials differ significantly.

Regarding anxiety levels, the data indicates that the utilization of video-assisted instructional materials has effectively reduced learners' anxiety, particularly in areas such as "The math section of standardized tests triggers a feeling of panic in me," "Holding a math textbook to study often makes me feel physically uncomfortable, like a stomach ache," "Presenting problems I can solve to the teacher makes me feel uneasy," "My worry about my grade makes it difficult for me to study effectively for math exams," "I struggle to pay attention to my math teachers," and "Learning that the next lesson is mathematics makes me feel nervous," all showing p-values less than 0.05. These findings highlight the positive influence of such instructional materials in reducing anxiety in math-related situations, thereby improving students' learning experiences. However, several statements did not show a statistically significant difference in anxiety levels post-intervention, suggesting that the impact of the materials varied across different aspects of anxiety. Overall, the average anxiety levels indicate a statistically significant decrease, reflecting the overall impact of the video-assisted instructional materials on reducing anxiety.

Regarding attitudes, the data reveals a significant change in learners' attitudes toward mathematics. Statements such as "Mathematics is a subject I am afraid of," "I am unable to think clearly when working with Mathematics," "I feel excited learning about Mathematics," "I feel happier in my mathematics class than in any other class," "Mathematics is not necessary in our country," "I don't enjoy going beyond the assigned work in Mathematics," "I study Mathematics just to pass the year level," and "I feel nervous in Mathematics class" all showed p-values less than 0.05. However, the average attitude from post-test to pre-test did not demonstrate a statistically significant difference. Some statements did not show statistically significant changes in attitudes post-intervention, with p-values greater than 0.05, indicating that students' attitude levels after implementing the video-assisted instructional materials differ significantly.

6. Significant Difference in Mathematical Skills of the Learners' before and after using the Video-Assisted Instructions.

The analysis revealed that there is strong evidence to suggest that the scores after the intervention (post-test) are significantly higher than the pre-test scores, with a p-value (Sig. 2-tailed) of 0.000. This suggests that the utilization of Video-Assisted Instruction in Mathematics 8 significantly enhances the mathematical skills of the learners.

7. The Comments and Suggestions given by the Validators to Improve the Developed Video-Assisted Instruction

The validators' comments on the Mathematics 8 video lessons highlight strengths such as clear and engaging presentations, effective use of prior knowledge, simple language, and well-defined objectives. Areas for improvement include keeping lessons concise, enhancing the visual presentation, addressing technical issues, improving the teacher's voice, incorporating a conversational tone, using appropriate graphics, and including a closing statement. This feedback provides valuable insights for researchers to refine video-assisted instruction, enhancing both visual and auditory experiences and ultimately improving the effectiveness of the lessons.

8. Enhanced audio-visual materials developed based on the findings

Video-Assisted Instruction is transforming education by using video lessons to enhance student engagement and mathematical skills. This intervention aims to address learning gaps and motivate struggling Mathematics 8 students at Bagupaye Integrated High School by developing their mathematical skills and improving their behavior. The enhanced audio-visual material is based on previous research findings.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions are drawn:

1. Video-Assisted Instruction is developed with careful consideration for several aspects; Content, format, presentation, and accuracy. Content should be relevant to learning objectives, engaging, and connected to real-world scenarios. Format should prioritize accessibility and high production quality, while presentation should be clear, concise, and visually appealing. Finally, accuracy and up-to-datedness are crucial, relying on credible sources and regular updates.
2. The study identified that the validity of video-assisted instructional materials is effective in content suitability and alignment with learning objectives, but improvements are necessary in promoting higher cognitive skills, desirable values, and safety warnings. While praised for sound quality, pacing, and balance between information and engagement, there are areas for enhancement in audio-visual effects, engagement strategies, and safety considerations to further improve effectiveness. Overall, the materials demonstrate high acceptability regarding effectiveness, presentation, and organization, with room for improvement in addressing typographical errors to maintain consistent accuracy and reliability.
3. The learners' behavior before, during, and after using various video-assisted instructions resulted in Grade 8 learners being focused and engaged in the classroom, providing opportunities for enhancing student engagement and optimizing the learning experience. This led to a significant increase in students' motivation levels, transitioning from "high" to "very high" motivation, improving engagement and enthusiasm for learning. Additionally, the study showed reduced anxiety levels and improved emotional well-being, creating a more positive academic environment, while further exploration and tailored interventions are required to enhance overall attitude improvements.
4. The learners' mathematical skills significantly improved after the Video-Assisted Instruction, as evidenced by notable progress in various competencies. Despite the substantial enhancement in skills and an increase in the overall mathematical skills score from 27.97 to 50.33, additional interventions are required to meet the desired 80% standard, highlighting the importance of ongoing targeted support to further enhance their mathematical abilities.
5. The study indicates a significant improvement in learners' motivation, enhancing their engagement and application of learning, although certain aspects of motivation require a tailored approach to address diverse needs. The effectiveness of the materials in enriching the learning experience is highlighted, with reduced anxiety levels observed in learners, particularly in panic triggers, discomfort, and grades, indicating potential enhancements in math-related scenarios. While significant changes in attitudes towards mathematics were noted, the average attitude change did not show a significant difference, suggesting varied impacts

across different aspects and revealing a diverse range of responses among students.

6. The null hypothesis for mathematical skills is rejected as there was a significant difference between the post-test and pre-test scores after the utilization of Video-Assisted Instruction as indicated by a p-value of 0.000. This suggests that the intervention is significantly effective in developing the mathematical skills of the learners on Mathematics 8.
7. The validators' feedback on the Mathematics 8 video lessons highlights both strengths, such as clear presentations and effective use of simple language, and areas for improvement. Their insights provide valuable guidance for researchers to enhance Video-Assisted Instruction, focusing on improving visual and auditory experiences to enhance lesson effectiveness and student engagement.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions, the following recommendations are offered:

1. Teachers can confidently utilize the validated Video-Assisted Instruction in Mathematics 8, as it has undergone rigorous evaluation and expert validation across key aspects, including content, format/technical design, presentation and organization, accuracy and up-to dateness of information. These materials have demonstrated effectiveness and suitability for classroom use, receiving passing scores in all areas. By incorporating these video lessons, teachers can enhance instruction, provide additional support to students, and improve learning outcomes in Mathematics 8. The endorsement of these materials by institutions, including school heads, further validates their quality and reliability, providing teachers with confidence in their use.
2. Based on the study findings, there is room for improvement in several areas. These include enhancing cognitive skills by promoting critical thinking and problem-solving, integrating core values like teamwork and creativity, and implementing safety measures to ensure a secure learning environment. Additionally, refining audio-visual elements, improving engagement strategies, and ensuring accuracy and reliability through thorough proofreading are essential. Therefore, the researcher recommends enhancing these areas to improve the validity and effectiveness of video-assisted instructional materials. By implementing these suggestions, video-assisted instructional materials can enhance their effectiveness, engagement, and impact on the learning experience, ultimately leading to improved performance of the students.
3. Given the positive improvements in student motivation, anxiety levels, overall engagement, and attitudes after using Video-Assisted Instructions. However, areas for improvement include supporting students who get discouraged when facing challenges and addressing specific concerns regarding attitudes, such as

nervousness and lack of confidence. The researchers recommend expanding engagement strategies to cater to diverse learning styles, tailoring interventions to address attitude concerns, continuously evaluating and adapting materials, promoting collaborative learning, and addressing technical issues. Continuous evaluation, encouraging collaboration, and addressing technical issues can provide a more engaging, motivating, and supportive learning environment for Grade 8 students.

4. Based on the findings, there was an improvement in students' mathematical skills after using Video-Assisted Instructions; nonetheless, the learners did not achieve the targeted 80% standard performance; nonetheless, the learners did not achieve the targeted 80% standard performance. Hence, the researcher recommends additional targeted interventions to meet the 80% standard. These include ongoing assessments, small group tutoring, individualized instruction, and supplemental resources. Differentiated instruction strategies, diverse learning styles, and engaging real-world scenarios can help students learn. Positive reinforcement, encouragement, and regular evaluations of the Video-Assisted Instruction and other interventions are essential for continuous improvement. By implementing these suggestions, students can develop their mathematical abilities and achieve the 80% standard performance.
5. Although there was a considerable improvement in learners' motivation, anxiety, and attitude following the implementation of video-assisted instructional materials in Mathematics 8, not all characteristics of motivation, anxiety, and attitude changed significantly. As a result, the researcher recommends a more tailored approach. To maximize success, educators should consider a tailored approach, regular evaluation, interactive content, feedback mechanisms, and real-world scenarios. Professional development opportunities can also help to boost the favourable effects of video-assisted instruction on learners' motivation, anxiety, attitude, and learning outcomes.
6. It has been found that the hypothesis is rejected. The analysis revealed significant difference in the learners' performance after using the video-assisted instructions. Therefore, it is recommended to adopt the use of Video-Assisted Instructional materials as a teaching strategy in teaching Mathematics 8. This adoption should be complemented by comprehensive teacher training on how to utilize them effectively and regular monitoring to guarantee that learners' academic performance improves over time. This intervention's established effectiveness justifies its widespread use to obtain higher mastery levels across the student population.
7. Based on the findings, the comments and suggestions of the validators highlight the crucial role of development in ensuring the quality and effectiveness of Video-Assisted Instruction before implementation. The study suggests that improvements to the Mathematics 8 video are essential to enhance students' overall learning experiences. Addressing identified areas for improvement will contribute to a smoother and more engaging learning environment.

8. For future researchers, a meta-analysis is recommended to synthesize findings from existing research on the implementation of Video-Assisted Instruction in developing learners' behavior and mathematical skills. Furthermore, future research could explore other aspects or variables that might impact the efficacy of these instructional materials, contributing to a more comprehensive understanding of their potential benefits.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The study ensured the informed consent was given to the following respondents. Freedom to withdraw from the study at any time, anonymity of the respondents was maintained, the respondents' well-being was safeguarded, no conflict of interests exists in the conduct of the study, plagiarism was strictly avoided, there was no bias in the interpretation of the findings and that the results were used purely for research.

Acknowledgments

The researcher wishes to express her heartfelt gratitude to the persons with wholehearted cooperation, support and guidance, especially to all who extended contribution and assistance in various ways towards the completion of this study and make this a reality.

First and foremost, the researcher thank our Almighty God, for the continuous blessings, strength, and wisdom bestowed upon her during this scholarly pursuit. It is through divine guidance that she has been able to make this study possible.

To Marinduque State College President Dr. Diosdado P. Zulueta, for his leadership and selfless assistance when needed;

To Dr. Leodegario M. Jalos, Jr., Chairperson of Extended Graduate Programs of Marinduque State College, for his untiring support, technical assistance and continuous guidance to the researcher in order for this study to be a success;

To Dr. Noel R. Palomares, her adviser, for his valuable suggestions, guidance and patience in checking this paper and for the enlightenment shared about the importance of this study;

To Engr. Willer A. Dayahan, her statistician, for his generously contributing time and expertise of this study;

To Mr. Jerome L. Lingon, her editor, for his invaluable assistance in checking the language structure of this manuscript;

To Dr. Gilbert C. Alva, her copy editor, for ensuring the consistency and accuracy of the language used throughout the study;

Members of the defense panel Dr. Diosdado P. Zulueta, Dr. Julieta Q. Nabos, and Dr. Rogel L. Limpiada for their invaluable contributions, their insights have been incredibly helpful for this study.

To Ms. Liezl M. Manoy; MSC's Support Staff, Graduate School, for her unending moral support;

To Mr. Crisar B. Borja, her husband, and her children for their unwavering love, support and encouragement that inspire her to pursue this study;

To Mr. Franklin R. Montiero and Mrs. Corazon M. Montiero, her parents and her siblings, for their love and sacrifices, have been the pillars of her resilience and determination. Your unwavering faith in her abilities has inspired her a lot to pursue this study.

To all of you, the researcher dedicate the completion of this study and express her heartfelt appreciation for your contributions, both seen and unseen, in making this achievement possible.

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